

CAIRT-PerReC

CAIRT Phase A Mission Performance and
Requirement Consolidation (PerReC) Activity

ESA/ESTEC contract 4000136480/21/NL/LF CCN1

Deliverable D-09

CAIRT measurement requirements assessment

Technical Note TN-3

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Reference Number: DEL-09-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-v3.1

Status: Final

Version/revision: 3.1 final

Date: 19-Nov-2025

<i>ESA Study Contract Report</i>		
<i>ESA Contract</i>	<i>Title</i>	<i>Contractor</i>
<i>4000136480/21/N L/LF CCN1</i>	<i>CAIRT measurement requirements assessment</i>	<i>Karlsruhe Institute of Technology</i>
<p><i>The CAIRT measurement requirements are discussed and their justification is supported by references to dedicated studies summarized in technical notes.</i></p> <p><i>The CAIRT L2 threshold performance is illustrated by linear 2d retrieval diagnostics performed with the SWB (Instrument simulator and LPE).</i></p> <p><i>The relative importance of different measurement requirements wrt their influence on L2 performance is presented.</i></p>		
<p>The work described in this report was done under ESA contract. Responsibility for the contents resides with the author(s) or organisation(s) that prepared it.</p>		
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DOCUMENT INFO

Reviewer

Reviewer	Organisation Short Name	E-Mail
All WP leader		

Document Control

Document version #	Date	Changes Made/Comments
1.0	14-Oct-2024	First version for MTR
2.0	1-Jul-2025	Added threshold requirement evaluation with linear SWB.
3.0	10-Oct-2025	Implemented answers to comments by Alex Hoffmann.
3.1	19-Nov-2025	Final editorial

Signature by issuing authority and/or lead author

List of acronyms

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1 Measurement requirements

Below the measurement requirement formulations are listed following version 0.4 of the MRD: [1].

1.1 Measurement requirements applicability

MR-M-070

Measurement requirements applicability

Unless otherwise stated, the measurement requirements shall be met:

- a) over the complete nominal lifetime;
- b) for the full radiance dynamic range;
- c) for each spectral sample;
- d) for each spatial sample;
- e) for unpolarised scenes;
- f) for spatially uniform scenes;
- g) for Level 1b (L1b) data; and
- h) with a confidence level of 68% (1σ if Gaussian distribution assumed applicable) for most knowledge requirements, and of 99.7% for most design or performance requirements.

Note 1: Unless otherwise stated the values stated as "larger (or smaller) than" have to be interpreted as including the specified value.

Note 2: Unless otherwise specified, requirements applicable to spatial (sub-)samples can be verified after binning from a finer physical to a virtual L1b grid defined by the coarsest (sub-)sampling permitted by the spatial sampling requirements, provided that any calculations for extrapolating or transforming to such a grid are clearly described and do not violate other requirements.

This point summarizes specific definitions for the measurement requirements to be applied in their respective analysis.

With respect to e), here a short clarification why polarization effects can be neglected given CAIRT's spectral range and focus:

In atmospheric radiative transfer, polarization of thermal light is introduced by scattering at molecules and particles (or reflection at surfaces). Since the major target of CAIRT is the observation of the direct light from thermal emission of molecules, no polarization is introduced. Also in the case of aerosol-observations, we concentrate on particulates with radii below 1 μm which allow us to neglect particle scattering [2], [3].

1.2 Apodization

MR-M-080

Apodisation

Requirements shall apply to non-apodised L1b data for clarity of definition. Norton Beer Strong (NBS) apodisation can be used for verification of requirements where appropriate and mentioned.

Note 1: NBS apodisation (ref to be added: <https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSA.66.000259>) is broadly used by scientific users before L2 processing. Thus, its use for requirement verification is consistent with the scientific use of the data, and allows direct linking to higher-level requirements.

- NBS references: [4], [5]
- The NBS apodization is applied in retrieval of MIPAS/Envisat data by the ESA processor [6] as well as scientific processors at KIT/Granada e.g. [7]
- Apodization has been shown to not decrease the information content of the retrieval but helps to save computation time by restricting the needed extension when spectral windows are used e.g. [8]

1.3 Spectral coverage

MR-M-090

Spectral coverage

The L1b data shall cover the thermal infrared spectral range from 718 cm⁻¹ (13.93 μm) to 2200 cm⁻¹ (4.55 μm).

Note 1: A gap in the spectral coverage between 1500 cm⁻¹ (6.67 μm) and 1590 cm⁻¹ (6.29 μm) is acceptable.

Note 2: A spectral gap in the L1b data implies that performance requirements are not applicable, and performance verification is not required in this gap; however, the spectral data in the gap are still to be provided.

Parent: MR-O-010 (constituents)

Justification was provided in [9]:

“The long wavelength cut-off is driven by the need for temperature retrievals from the CO₂ band, with the Q-branch at 718 cm⁻¹. Good temperature knowledge is essential for all CAIRT objectives.

The short wavelength cut-off is driven by the need to observe emission spectra of CO and NO, essential parameters for Objectives A, D and F. Figures 11 and 12 (in [9]) provide forward calculations for tangent altitudes of 10 km and 90 km, respectively, indicating the spectral signatures in the different wavenumber regions.

A gap in the spectral coverage between 1500 cm⁻¹ (6.67 μm) and 1590 cm⁻¹ (6.29 μm) is acceptable. A spectral gap in the data implies that performance requirements are not applicable in this gap; however, the spectral data in the gap is still to be provided. Wavenumbers higher than 1590 cm⁻¹ are required for NO₂ retrievals, which is a prime target parameter of the CAIRT mission.”

Schemes for selection of optimised spectral windows for infrared limb-emission sounding with high spectral resolution were mainly developed for MIPAS/Envisat data analysis [10], [11], [12].

For requirement consolidation of CAIRT, we have used the altitude-dependent microwindow selection for MIPAS/Envisat retrievals performed at IMK/IAA – only slightly adapted to the CAIRT wavenumber-grid. This database has the advantage, that it covers the whole wavelength as well as the whole altitude-region of CAIRT. Furthermore, as it has been used to analyse the entire MIPAS/Envisat dataset the results of which have been validated, published and used in a wealth of scientific analyses (<https://www.imk-asf.kit.edu/english/3052.php>). These spectral windows are plotted in Figure 2.

Additionally, for specific investigations on the dependence of estimated uncertainties derived from 1d linear retrievals on the used spectral ranges, also different microwindow-sets have been applied: Figure 3 shows the standard MIPAS/Envisat set used for ESA-retrievals. These windows have been adopted to the spectral grid of CAIRT as well as continued to higher altitudes. Mind that the number of retrieved species is less than in the case of MIPAS/Envisat IMK/IAA dataset. Further, as shown in Figure 4, a dedicated CAIRT

micro window set has been derived. This set is optimized specifically only with respect to spectral noise (NESR), and, thus, encompasses generally more spectral information than both other datasets.

Figure 1 Radiative Transfer Model calculations of limb spectral radiances at 100 km (row 1), 50 km (row 2) and 10 km (rows 3 and 4) tangent point altitudes, for individual trace gases and an ERS daytime model atmosphere (45°N, April). NESR requirements are also shown. Bottom, approximate locations of retrieval micro-windows per parameter, grouped by Mission Objectives

Figure 2 Altitude-dependent CAIRT baseline microwindow set. X-axis: wavenumber (cm^{-1}), y-axis: tangent altitude (km). Different colors are used to distinguish the single spectral windows.

Figure 4 As Figure 2 but for the extended CAIRT microwindows.

1.4 Spectral resolution

MR-M-100

Spectral resolution

The L1b data spectral resolution, defined as the Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) of the Instrument Spectral Response Function (ISRF), shall be $\leq 0.25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [goal: 0.125 cm^{-1}].

Note 1: This requirement corresponds to a spectral resolution of 0.4 cm^{-1} [goal: 0.2 cm^{-1}] for NBS apodised data. Verification can be performed with apodised or unapodised data and the appropriate requirement.

Note 2: For scientific requirement assessments, spectral sampling of 0.2 cm^{-1} [goal: 0.1 cm^{-1}] are assumed, linking spectral resolution and sampling through a sinc function in terms of an ideal FTS ISRF, and a factor of 1.2.

Parent: MR-O-010 (constituents)

Justification was provided in [9].

This requirement corresponds to a spectral resolution of 0.4 cm^{-1} [goal: 0.2 cm^{-1}] for NBS apodised data. Verification can be performed with apodised or unapodised data and the appropriate requirement.

Strong oversampling is to be avoided, and the grid is to have a finite representation. For scientific requirement assessments, spectral sampling of 0.2 cm^{-1} [goal: 0.1 cm^{-1}] are assumed, linking spectral resolution and sampling through a sinc function in terms of an ideal FTS ISRF, and a factor of 1.2.

Requirements for spectral resolution are based on extensive experience with MIPAS/ENVISAT (in full- and reduced resolution modes), studies performed for EE7 candidate PREMIER, and in particular the airborne demonstrator GLORIA. GLORIA has higher spectral resolution than the CAIRT goal, so that the effect of spectral resolution has been studied based on real GLORIA observed spectra.

In [13], retrieval tests using GLORIA balloon data obtained during a flight on 21/22 August 2021 with different spectral resolutions ($\text{OPD}_{\text{max}} = 8 \text{ cm}$, $\text{OPD}_{\text{max}} = 5 \text{ cm}$, $\text{OPD}_{\text{max}} = 2.5 \text{ cm}$) have revealed that even with the lowest spectral resolution a derivation of reliable SF_6 vertical profiles seems to be possible, at least in altitude regions from the upper troposphere up to the middle stratosphere where the SF_6 signal in the spectra is not too weak. However, the noise error increases using lower spectral resolutions (with fixed altitude resolution). Hence, in the case of low spectral resolution, it will be necessary to average multiple individual SF_6 profiles to get rid of noisy structures. Using the coarsest investigated spectral resolution is principally possible (but far from optimal) in the case of SF_6 . However, the results of these SF_6 retrieval tests cannot be directly transferred to other trace gases. Hence, $\text{OPD}_{\text{max}} = 2.5 \text{ cm}$ should be regarded as the lower limit of a spectral resolution that can still be recommended for atmospheric applications of instruments like CAIRT.

1.5 ISRF knowledge

MR-M-110

ISRF knowledge

The ISRF shall be characterised with a relative uncertainty of $\leq 1\%$ of its peak value in the spectral range where its envelope is above the 1% value.

Note 1: An ISRF model for the instrument is expected to allow simulation of the ISRF as a function of key parameters such as spectral position, position of a pixel in the field-of-view, instrument temperature, chosen maximum Optical Path Difference (OPD), etc. On-ground instrument characterisation must then demonstrate that the model represents the instrument behaviour with the required accuracy for typical in-flight situations and parameterisations.

Note 2: Compliance with the requirement can be demonstrated with NBS apodised data and with any appropriate characterisation source (gas cell, laser).

Note 3: This requirement is applicable on the physical spatial sub-sample grid (on which an ISRF model is to be provided).

Parent: MR-O-010 (uncertainty)

ISRF the knowledge requirement has been tested by linear uncertainty assessment (LPE calculations) through a variation of the half-width of the unapodized sinc-function by 1% [14][this document chapter 3]. The effect on such a change is shown in Figure 5. This way of perturbation which is symmetric with respect to the ISRF-center is in first order independent from an asymmetric perturbation of the ISRF-function which would be introduced by a shift along the wavenumber axis. The latter one, however, is covered by the spectral calibration and, therefore, not included in these considerations.

Comparing with other systematic instrumental uncertainties (Figure 16) the knowledge of the ISRF plays an important role within the uncertainty budget. Within the systematic and calibration uncertainties, the ISRF is a leading source of uncertainty for upper tropospheric and stratospheric water vapour and stratospheric CH₄, N₂O, HNO₃, as well as CO above about 75 km.

Figure 5 Spectral range within the CO2 laser band showing the effect of changing the ISRF-width by 1%.

1.6 Absolute spectral knowledge

MR-M-120

Absolute spectral knowledge

The position of each spectral sample centre $\tilde{\nu}_i$ shall be known with an absolute uncertainty ($|d\tilde{\nu}_{abs}(\tilde{\nu}_i)/\tilde{\nu}_i|$) of ≤ 2 ppm [goal: ≤ 1 ppm] at L1b.

Note 1: The absolute value $d\tilde{\nu}_{abs}$ (in cm^{-1}) for the knowledge of any spectral sample is obtained by multiplying the specified value (in ppm) by its spectral position $\tilde{\nu}_i$.

Note 2: The specified spectral knowledge is expected to be achievable via atmospheric line calibration after securing hardware-based spectral knowledge to within 50-100 ppm.

Note 3: Sufficient radiometric accuracy – and spectral stability that enables averaging over multiple radiance spectra – is needed to facilitate spectral calibration to the specified spectral knowledge.

Parent: MR-O-010 (uncertainty)

The uncertainties introduced by knowledge of the wavenumber axis have been investigated in [15] and [this document chapter 3] on basis of LPE 2d linear retrieval simulations.

In [16] and [this document chapter 3], spectral accuracy has been estimated by linear regression of the spectral shift errors from retrievals at 11 dedicated microwindows (extended IMK/IAA selection) covering the 750–1950 cm^{-1} range. The spectral shift retrieval used spectra from all spatial samples with tangent heights > 25 km of one single acquisition. Both systematic and random uncertainty components of the spectral shift retrieval have been estimated. The resulting spectral uncertainties have been propagated into uncertainties of the atmospheric targets. Largest uncertainties result in case of HCFC-22. However, these are with 4% of the requirement uncertainty, these are minor (Figure 16).

As a pre-condition for the above applied spectral shift retrieval in L2-analysis a reduction of a larger shift uncertainty to 2 ppm has been studied the results of which are described in the following.

In [15], a dedicated study has shown that:

- Even with a relatively easy and straight-forward fast model (which does not involve a dedicated retrieval process [16], [this document chapter 3]), a converging spectral fit starting with a large error (0.3 cm^{-1}) is possible
- The quality of the wavenumber-calibration increases strongly with temporal averaging.
- Above about 50 km, only very few windows allow for a good fit of better than 2 ppm. However, in an imaging FTS instrument, the spectral axis is strongly correlated across the sensor. This can be used to constrain the results to other altitudes where the atmospheric signal is not sufficient.
- Best fits with possible windows scattered over the whole wavelength range are reached between 20 and 50 km of tangent altitude.

The following results are achieved in [15] for a 1d-profile retrieval and have to be regarded as first indications for the more detailed analysis using the LPE 2d retrieval approach as described above.

- For species with broad-band spectral features, like the CFCs, N₂O₅, PAN, H₂SO₄, the retrieval error due to spectral uncertainties is negligible
- Species with more localized features, the wavenumber-shift uncertainty of 2 ppm introduces often larger retrieval errors and depend strongly on the set of chosen spectral windows (e.g. H₂O).
- Largest errors of up to 20% of the requirement threshold values in the different altitude regions appear in case of temperature, H₂O, O₃ and NO₂-retrievals.

These results point towards the following approach to correct for spectral uncertainties:
L1 data to be corrected using atmospheric lines to better than 2 ppm within the L1-processing as prerequisite (1) for the following spectral 'shift' retrieval in L2, and, (2) as probably sufficient accuracy for use of L1-radiances directly in data assimilation of e.g. temperature and major trace-gases. That this second application might be feasible with an uncertainty of the spectral axis of 2 ppm was hinted at in [15] and should be examined and verified further.

1.7 Relative spectral knowledge

MR-M-130

Relative spectral knowledge

The relative spectral position of any L1b spectral sample centre to that of any other L1b spectral sample centre shall be known with a relative uncertainty ($d\tilde{\nu}_{rel}(\tilde{\nu}_i)/\tilde{\nu}_i$) of ≤ 1 ppm [goal: ≤ 0.4 ppm].

Note 1: The relative total uncertainty can be computed from the absolute total uncertainty as follows:

$$d\tilde{\nu}_{rel}(\tilde{\nu}_i)/\tilde{\nu}_i = |\max(d\tilde{\nu}_{abs}(\tilde{\nu}_i)/\tilde{\nu}_i) - \min(d\tilde{\nu}_{abs}(\tilde{\nu}_i)/\tilde{\nu}_i)|$$

Note 2: The precise position of spectral samples will be co-retrieved during L2 product processing within appropriate spectral microwindows (“spectral shift retrieval”). This requirement ensures that spectral shifts retrieved in these microwindows can be extrapolated to other retrieval regions across the spectral range.

Parent: MR-O-010 (uncertainty)

The spectral shift retrieval described above uses spectra from all spatial samples with tangent heights above 25 km of any single acquisition, and retrieves the shift in dedicated spectral microwindows. The spectral shift correction in ppm is then estimated by a linear regression of the individual shift retrieval results across all microwindows to produce the wavenumber-dependent correction function (see Figure 6 below). To ensure applicability over the entire wavenumber range, the gradient m of the linear model needs to be constrained by the relative uncertainty $d\tilde{\nu}_{rel}(\tilde{\nu}_i)/\tilde{\nu}_i$. This side-condition to the linearity of the spectral axis was applied for the LPE uncertainty estimation of the spectral shift retrieval in [this document chapter 3]. A relative uncertainty of 1 ppm was found to be sufficient to avoid resulting spectral shift uncertainties (after the shift retrieval) at any spectral gridpoint to exceed significantly the uncertainty at the center of the spectral sample (see Figures 42 and 43).

Figure 6 Illustration of spectral knowledge requirements (MR-M-120 and MR-M-130). Left, schematic representation of spectral calibration, with absolute and relative knowledge shown as uncertainties on an absolute wavenumber axis. Right, schematic representation of spectral knowledge expressed on a relative scale (in ppm), and illustrating the final spectral shift retrieval process in dedicated microwindows (as part of L2 processing) and its linear extrapolation to higher wavenumbers, using a constrained least-squares fit. Here, $\tilde{\nu}_0 = 1459 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is the central wavenumber across the CAIRT range, with the constraint that $|m| \leq (d\tilde{\nu}_{rel}(\tilde{\nu}_i)/\tilde{\nu}_i) / (\tilde{\nu}_{\max} - \tilde{\nu}_{\min})$.

1.8 Field-of-View at geometric tangent point surface – vertical

MR-M-140

Field-of-View at geometric tangent point surface – vertical

The CAIRT mission shall provide L1b limb radiance measurement data for geometric tangent points covering a minimum altitude range from ≤ 5 km [goal: 4 km] to ≥ 105 km [goal: ≥ 115 km].

Note 1: Altitude is specified as geodetic altitude above the WGS84 reference ellipsoid.

Note 2: Atmospheric refraction implies that the lowermost real tangent altitude will be lower than the geometric tangent altitude.

Parent: MR-O-040

In limb-sounding geometry, the altitude range where the retrieval of vertically resolved distributions of atmospheric parameters is possible, is defined by the range of measured tangent points. Therefore, this requirement directly follows from the required altitude range of atmospheric target quantities.

1.9 Field-of-View at geometric tangent point surface – across-track (swath)

MR-M-150

Field-of-View at geometric tangent point surface – across-track (swath)

The CAIRT mission shall provide L1b limb radiance measurement data for geometric tangent points covering an across-track range (“swath”) at the lowermost tangent point of ≥ 300 km [goal: 500 km] width.

Note 1: The across-track range provided spans from the corner of the left-most sample to the corner of the right-most sample, in a straight line (“chord”) and at the bottom of the field-of-view (FoV).

Parent: MR-O-080

An across-track field of view width of at least 300 km is necessary to achieve the requirements for L2b data regarding gravity wave analysis. This may be argued as follows: The largest gravity wavelength in zonal direction which still can be reliably recovered is about 3-5 times the track width. 300km trackwidth hence allow for roughly 1500 km horizontal wavelength which encompasses most of the GW spectrum[17]. This is underlined by the Monte Carlo analysis (cf. Figure 7) of the wave direction uncertainty for the strongest wave component and at 35km, an altitude favourable for the inference of GW parameters (DEL-07-02-GW-Monte-Carlo). The wave direction exceeds the threshold of 7.5° at $\log_{10}(k)=-3.2$ corresponding to 1500 km. For low altitudes or beyond 60km and for higher wave components this limit is reached even faster. In addition, a track-width of 300 km is a minimum for a clean scale separation between planetary scale waves and GWs (Task-4 report; detrending of "GW observations from space" (PREMIER); Preusse et al. 2012).

Figure 7 Uncertainty estimate (cf. DEL-07-02-GW-Monte-Carlo) of the wave direction for a cuboid size of 275 km across-track (pixel center to pixel center) and 450 km along track at 35 km altitude (low noise, low influence of planetary scale waves).

Apart from gravity-waves, an across-track sampling further helps to resolve horizontally fast varying distributions due to smaller-scale processes, like volcanic eruptions, biomass-burning, streamers of ozone and water-vapour in the UTLS. Further, it enhances the probability of sounding less cloud-affected scenes during limb-imaging in the mid-upper troposphere.

Figure 8 Statistical analysis of revisit time at 20-km altitude. Left, number of times that tracked moving air parcels have been observed after 3 days with 400 km swath. Middle, fraction of parcels revisited at least once within 3 days as a function of swath and latitude region. Right, violin plots of distribution of average revisit times for air parcels observed with 400-km swath. The superimposed boxplot shows the interquartile range, with bars for mean in cyan and median in red.

1.10 Limb measurement minimum altitude across-track

MR-M-160

Limb measurement minimum altitude across-track

The minimum altitude as per MR-M-140 shall be achieved across the swath as per MR-M-150.

Note 1: This requirement provides for the effect of across-track horizon curvature on tangent point altitudes.

Parent: MR-O-040

This requirement follows directly from the requirement of the retrieval target quantities' altitude ranges which is valid across the swath.

1.11 Spatial sampling – vertical

MR-M-170

Spatial sampling – vertical

The L1b vertical Spatial Sampling Distance (SSD) shall be ≤ 1 km below 80 km of altitude, and ≤ 2 km above, at the centre of the swath. A degradation of up to 20% is acceptable for geometry variations across the horizontal field-of-view.

Note 1: Preference is for a regular 1-km SSD to be maintained above 80 km of altitude, and for any necessary binning to be carried out within the L2 ground processing.

Parent: MR-O-060

[9]: Requirements for vertical spatial sampling distance follow from the scientific Level-2 requirements of 1 km (goal) vertical resolution for key parameters.

This requirement together with “1.16 SEDF/crosstalk performance – vertical” determine the vertical resolution achievable by limb measurements. LPE calculation have demonstrated that with these combinations (1 km vertical sampling/ 1.4 km SEDF width), the required threshold vertical resolution is met nearly everywhere albeit with some restrictions for tropospheric and upper stratospheric water vapor, upper atmospheric CO and stratospheric SO₂ [16] and [this document chapter 3] (**Figure 14**), where the ‘hvxres’ resolution requirements are met (i.e. combination of horizontal and vertical resolution). This implies that the chosen sampling in combination with the SEDF width (and retrieval regularization weighting horizontal vs. vertical resolution) are sufficient but should not be relaxed further.

1.12 Spatial sampling – across-track (ACT)

MR-M-180

Spatial sampling – across-track (ACT)

The L1b across-track Spatial Sampling Distance (SSD) shall be ≤ 50 km, at the centre of the swath. A degradation of up to 20% is acceptable for geometry variations across the horizontal field-of-view.

Parent: MR-O-070

Together with the across-track horizontal SEDF performance (MR-M-280), an ACT SSD of 50 km is sufficient to meet the L2a horizontal spatial resolution requirements, nominally set around a 100-km goal value, except for the temperature product specified down to 50 km. The 50-km ACT L1b sampling is aligned with the 50-km ALT sampling from MR-M-210, providing a regular horizontal measurement grid in both directions.

1.13 Spatial sub-sampling – across-track (ACT)

MR-M-190

Spatial sub-sampling – across-track (ACT)

Across-track L1b data shall be provided on a sub-sampling grid of ≤ 25 km.

Note 1: Degradation in sensitivity (NESR) for any smaller SSD compared to the nominal value follows the scaling law as per MR-M-390, provided the spatial samples remain contiguous (no gaps).

Parent: MR-O-070

A sub-sampling of the ACT sampling is essential for gravity wave analysis (see Fig 5, chapter 2.1.4 in [18]). The figure shows that a substantial part of GWMF is at scales of 100-200 km. This part is resolved only properly in the data for across-track sampling of 25 km as substantial oversampling over the Nyquist limit is required. Furthermore, across a pixel the signal is averaged, which suppresses 100 km waves by less than 10% for <25 km pixel size, but by almost 40% for 50 km pixel size (cf. Equation 11 of [19]).

A second benefit is the possibility to deselect cloud-influenced observations. As evaluated in [20] the improvement between 400 km across-track and having 25-km wide bins is often around 100% at lower altitudes and cloud-affected regions, while for a 100 km across-track field-of-view the typical improvement is around 25% when going to 25-km bins.

1.14 Regular pixel binning – across-track (ACT)

MR-M-200

Regular pixel binning – across-track (ACT)

Sub-samples shall contain the same number of detector “read pixels” across the swath.

Note 1: This number for pixel-binning to sub-sample size includes any dead/bad pixels, which will however be masked and will not contribute to the integrated radiance of the sub-sample.

Note 2: This requirement may be met through additional on-ground binning of downlinked data.

This requirement is set to ensure that the across-track sub-samples are regular in size – bar the geometric effects associated with projecting detector iFoVs onto the tangent point surface. A regular sub-sampling grid is needed to simplify the processing of L2b gravity wave parameters.

1.15 Spatial sampling – along-track (ALT)

MR-M-210

Spatial sampling – along-track (ALT)

The L1b along-track Spatial Sampling Distance (SSD) shall be ≤ 50 km.

Note 1: The along-track SSD is assumed to be associated with spacecraft displacement over the time associated with a measurement cycle (acquisition of all spectra over the entire altitude range and over the full swath).

Note 2: This corresponds to an acquisition time of approximately 7 to 8 s at spacecraft velocity.

Parent: MR-O-070

The measurement geometry of CAIRT is designed that along-track and along-LOS coincide. Radiative transfer annihilates waves shorter than 150 km (for vertical wavelengths longer than 5 km) in the observed radiances [19]. These shortest waves, however, have to be properly sampled in order to avoid retrieval artefacts [21]. This requires sampling of 50 km or better. That a 50 km sampling along-track is sufficient, is shown in Fig 5, chapter 2.1.4 in [18]. Along-track sampling is also accounted for in LPE sensitivity analysis [16] and [this document chapter 3](**Figure 14**). There, the horizontal resolution figures are in most cases between goal and threshold while cases better than goal and those around the threshold values are in a balanced relation to one another (**Figure 12**). There, the horizontal resolution figures are in most cases between goal and threshold.

1.16 SEDF/crosstalk performance – vertical

MR-M-220

SEDF performance – vertical

The vertical FWHM of the System Energy Distribution Function (SEDF) shall be ≤ 1.5 [goal: ≤ 1.2] km across the entire spectral range and ≤ 1.4 km for wavenumbers $\geq 780 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ below 80 km of altitude, and ≤ 3 [goal: ≤ 2.4] km across the entire spectral range at higher altitudes.

Note 1: This requirement constrains the effective vertical resolution of the imaging system.

Parent: MR-O-010

MR-M-230

Spatial crosstalk performance – vertical (near-field)

The vertical spatial crosstalk shall be $\leq 9\%$ for the first neighbour, $\leq 3\%$ for the second neighbour, and $\leq 2\%$ for the third neighbour.

Note 1: This requirement is applicable on the physical spatial sub-sample grid.

Note 2: This requirement constrains the near-field shape of the SEDF and thus the parasitic signal from the wings of the SEDF. Crosstalk contains all the elements included in the SEDF definition.

Note 3: Real crosstalk performance in the near-field may exceed the values specified above by up to 50% to account for other SEDF shapes representing the imaging system more realistically.

MR-M-240

Spatial crosstalk performance – vertical (far-field)

Beyond the third neighbour, the vertical spatial crosstalk shall be below the values provided in Figure 4.17 (right) for 20-km broad intervals. The top row provides the goal specification (9, 3, 2, 1, 0.5, 0.1%), the bottom row the threshold (20, 12, 9, 6, 3, 1%) specification.

Note 1: This requirement is applicable on the physical spatial sub-sample grid.

Note 2: This requirement constrains far-field vertical crosstalk, to limit contamination of faint signals in the upper regions of the atmosphere by stronger signals from below.

1.17 SEDF knowledge – vertical

MR-M-250	SEDF knowledge – vertical
The vertical FWHM of the SEDF shall be known to $\leq 2\%$.	
<i>Note 1: This requirement implies “in-flight” knowledge over the mission lifetime, including on-ground characterisation, launch and on-orbit stability.</i>	
<i>Note 2: This requirement is applicable on the physical spatial sub-sample grid.</i>	
<i>Parent: MR-O-010 (uncertainties)</i>	
MR-M-260	SEDF knowledge – vertical (near-field)
The vertical SEDF shall be known to within ≤ 0.01 relative to the SEDF centre maximum value between 1.5 and 2.5 km of the SEDF centre position.	
<i>Note 1: This requirement is applicable on the physical spatial sub-sample grid.</i>	
<i>Note 2: The vertical region of 1.5 to 2.5 km covers the second neighbouring sample for 1-km samples. The first neighbour is strongly affected by the SEDF FWHM knowledge requirement, which is why it is omitted here.</i>	
<i>Note 3: An SEDF model is expected to be provided that is applicable to each spatial sub-sample. The vertical SEDF model is used for L2 product retrievals. SEDF has a high spatial and spectral correlation. The characterisation of the model can be done using significantly lower spatial and spectral resolution than for atmospheric measurements.</i>	
<i>Note 4: For each line-of-sight associated with a spatial sub-sample (ij), the vertical SEDF model needs to be provided in angular (as a function of elevation angle θ) and spectral (as a function of wavenumber k) space, i.e. $SEDF_{VER,ijk}(\theta)$. A discretised description is acceptable.</i>	
<i>Parent: MR-O-010 (uncertainties)</i>	
MR-M-270	SEDF knowledge – vertical (far-field)
The vertical SEDF shall be known to within: $\leq 5.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ relative to the SEDF centre maximum value between 2.5 and 5.5 km of the SEDF centre position; $\leq 6.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ relative to the SEDF centre maximum value between 5.5 and 20.5 km of the SEDF centre position; $\leq 1.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ relative to the SEDF centre maximum value between 20.5 and 60.5 km of the SEDF centre position; $\leq 5.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$ relative to the SEDF centre maximum value between 60.5 km of the SEDF centre position and the edge of the vertical FoV (115 km).	
<i>Note 1: This requirement is applicable on the physical spatial sub-sample grid.</i>	
<i>Note 2: The vertical region beyond 2.5 km covers neighbouring samples beyond sample 2 (for 1-km samples) and up to the edge of the vertical FoV.</i>	
<i>Note 3: This requirement controls the uncertainty on far-field vertical SEDF knowledge.</i>	
<i>Note 4: The SEDF knowledge in this requirement is to be achieved via in-flight full-field SEDF retrieval using the L1b spectral radiance data across the full FoV, by fitting a parametric vertical SEDF model that needs to be established via on-ground characterisation.</i>	
<i>Parent: MR-O-010 (uncertainties)</i>	

All vertical SEDF requirements:

The knowledge about the central part of the SEDF was investigated in [this document chapter 3] by evaluation the effect of an assumed knowledge uncertainty of the SEDF half-width. This resulted in low related uncertainties in the 2d linear LPE retrievals of target quantities relative to other sources of uncertainty (Figure 16).

The knowledge about the central part of the SEDF was investigated in [this document chapter 3] by evaluation the effect of an assumed knowledge uncertainty of the SEDF half-width. This resulted in low related uncertainties in the 2d linear LPE retrievals of target quantities relative to other sources of uncertainty (Figure 16).

The effect of the knowledge and performance of the far-field of the SEDF has been studied in [22] where a typical diffraction function has been applied within LPE calculations and the reaction of the retrieval of a knowledge error related to this diffraction function. In [23] the resulting cross-talk values from a realistic vertical SEDF have been discussed. Requirements for the near and far-field of the SEDF have been proposed. The resulting requirements on near and far-field knowledge of the SEDF have been finally tested in [this document chapter 3] and are summarized in Figure 16.

Requirements for the far-field SEDF are relatively tight, and may be challenging to meet via on-ground characterisation and to maintain in-flight over the mission lifetime. An in-flight SEDF retrieval process based on L1b spectral radiance data fitting across the full FoV is foreseen to constrain the input for L2a retrievals: this will be based on parametric fitting of a vertical SEDF model previously established via on-ground characterisation. The viability of this approach has been established via a proof-of-concept retrieval routine and sensitivity studies.

1.18 SEDF performance – across-track (ACT)

MR-M-280 **SEDF performance – across-track (ACT)**
 The horizontal FWHM of the System Energy Distribution Function (SEDF) shall not exceed the horizontal SSD by more than 10%.

Note 1: The horizontal SSD applicable to this requirement is specified as per MR-M-190.

Note 2: This requirement is applicable on the physical spatial sub-sample grid.

Parent: MR-O-070

An across-track horizontal FWHM of the SEDF that does not exceed the sub-samples' SSD by more than 10% avoids significant optical blurring induced by the imaging system, while at the same time not imposing too challenging a technical constraint on the imaging system compared to the vertical SEDF requirement. This ACT spatial resolution of the L1b data is deemed sufficient for retrieving the geophysical data products most demanding in terms of horizontal resolution, that is, the gravity waves L2b parameters (TBC).

MR-M-290 **Horizontal scene mixing performance – across-track (ACT)**
 The integral of the across-track SEDF calculated outside the edges of a physical sub-sample shall be $\leq 15\%$ of the total sub-sample SEDF, combining left and right sides.

Note 1: This requirement is applicable on the physical spatial sub-sample grid.

MR-M-290 is an updated requirement based on a bottom-up system proposal that has not been assessed or justified yet. It is not expected to be a mission performance critical requirement, though impact of relaxation may need to be evaluated (TBC).

MR-M-300 **SEDF performance – horizon curvature effect**
 The integral of the SEDF within a vertical band of width equivalent to the required threshold value of the vertical SEDF FWHM (MR-M-220) shall not differ by more than 5% over all sub-samples of a horizontal row.

Note 1: This requirement addresses the tilt of the SEDF with respect to the Earth surface, towards the edges of the swath (horizon curvature effect).

Note 2: The lines delimiting the vertical band are both parallel to the Earth tangent at the sub-tangent point, and orthogonal to the line-of-sight.

Note 3: This requirement may affect the maximum horizontal extent of sub-samples at the edge of the swath.

MR-M-300 is an updated requirement based on a bottom-up system proposal that has not been assessed or justified yet. It is not expected to be a mission performance critical requirement, though impact of relaxation may need to be evaluated (TBC).

1.19 SEDF knowledge – across-track (ACT)

MR-M-305

SEDF knowledge – across-track (ACT)

The horizontal SEDF shall be known to within ≤ 0.02 relative to the SEDF centre maximum value. (TBC)

Note 1: The information on the horizontal SEDF knowledge is required at steps of size equivalent to a sub-sample. (TBC)

Note 2: This requirement is applicable on the physical spatial sub-sample grid.

MR-M-305 is a new requirement that was introduced with the update of MR-M-290. The need for this requirement and its justification are TBC.

1.20 Pointing performance - vertical

MR-M-310

Altitude pointing absolute performance

The lowermost geometric tangent point altitudes of both samples defining the edges of the across-track FoV shall be maintained within a vertical tolerance of ≤ 1 km of their nominal value with a confidence level of 99% over time.

Note 1: This requirement provides for long-term absolute pointing accuracy, including in pitch and in roll.

Parents: MR-M-140 and MR-M-160

In 1.8 (Field-of-View at geometric tangent point surface – vertical), a minimum altitude range to be covered is defined. Here, it is ensured that the altitude pointing is not drifting more than one pixel width.

MR-M-360

Pointing stability (performance) – vertical

The vertical stability of a geometric tangent point over the acquisition time of any single interferogram shall be ≤ 25 m (when calculated as the Root Mean Square Error) and ≤ 65 m maximum peak amplitude; both conditions shall apply for a confidence level of 99% when evaluated over any orbit.

Note 1: A Gaussian white noise distribution of vertical jitter amplitudes between 0.1 and 500 Hz has been assumed for evaluating the requirement, calculated as [...]. Better performance (lower jitter) is beneficial.

Note 2: This requirement is also understood to constrain the maximum permissible vertical pointing drift during any single interferogram acquisition – compared to ideal line-of-sight elevation pointing with respect to an absolute reference (e.g., WGS84 ellipsoid) – to within ± 65 m.

Parent: MR-O-010 (uncertainties)

Extensive tests with respect to pointing-jitter as baseline for this requirement have been performed and are reported in [24]. Results from that report have been used for the threshold performance calculations as described below in section 2.3.3. As can be seen from Figure 16, the LOS stability is the second major source of uncertainty at lowest altitudes in case of NO, OCS, SO₂, H₂SO₄-liq and the third most important source in case of O₃, SF₆, N₂O, and CO. At higher altitudes, no strong contribution to the total uncertainty is estimated.

1.21 Pointing knowledge - vertical

MR-M-320

Absolute geolocation knowledge

The absolute geolocation knowledge of a geometric tangent point corresponding to the centre of an L1b spatial sample shall be ≤ 500 m [goal: 200 m] in altitude, and ≤ 2 km in both horizontal directions (across- and along-track), with a confidence level of 99% over time.

Note 1: Pointing angles (elevation and azimuth) for the lines-of-sight of each spatial sample (or subunit thereof), spacecraft PVT, and their uncertainties, are to be provided with the data products.

Parent: MR-O-090

For the retrieval of target quantities in limb-sounding, good pointing information, especially with respect to viewing elevation (i.e. tangent altitude) is required. In [16] and [this document chapter 3], it has been shown that when the retrieval of pointing is performed together with the retrieval of atmospheric temperature, sufficient information on pointing can be derived to be fed into the subsequent retrieval of trace-gases and aerosols. Such an approach is standard in case of IR limb-emission measurements (e.g. [6], [25], [26]). Therefore, the coarse a-priori vertical pointing knowledge as required here is sufficient to enter the retrieval chain.

MR-M-330

Relative geolocation knowledge – spatial (intra-band)

The relative vertical geolocation knowledge between two geometric tangent points corresponding to the centres of any two L1b spatial samples shall be ≤ 100 m, within one spectral band and for each spectral sample.

Note 1: This requirement is intended to also include the impact of insufficiently characterised distortions across the field-of-view, assumed to be spatially correlated.

Parent: MR-O-010 (uncertainties)

This requirement was examined via LPE calculations in [16] and [this document chapter 3]. Since relative vertical geolocation uncertainties are strongly spatially correlated, a linear error model (in the vertical) is assumed. Further, since the LOS retrieval is most sensitive at the lower altitudes, relative pointing errors are compensated, there. For this reason, the linear error model is constrained to zero at the lower edge, while the displacement at the upper edge is simulated randomly on 100 MC ensemble members with a standard deviation corresponding to the relative geolocation knowledge value. As can be seen in Figure 16 the intra-band geolocation knowledge in general has a share of less than 10% of the total uncertainty (only in case of H₂O about 10% in the upper troposphere). Thus, this requirement is judged as appropriate.

MR-M-340

Relative geolocation knowledge – spectral (intra-band)

The relative vertical geolocation knowledge between two geometric tangent points corresponding to the centres of any two L1b spectral samples of the same spatial sample shall be ≤ 25 m within one spectral band. (TBC)

Note 1: This requirement is intended to also include the impact of insufficiently characterised chromatic aberrations.

Parent: MR-O-010 (uncertainties)

With ≤ 25 m uncertainty in the relative vertical geolocation of spectral samples associated with the same spatial sample, MR-M-340 constrains the intra-band spectral relative vertical pointing uncertainties to only a slight modulation of the MR-M-330 spatial relative vertical pointing uncertainties, with impacts on L2a products expected to be negligible (TBC).

MR-M-350

Relative geolocation knowledge (inter-band)

The relative vertical geolocation knowledge of a geometric tangent point corresponding to the centre of any L1b spatial sample to that of any other L1b spatial sample shall be ≤ 100 m between samples of two different spectral bands.

Note 1: This requirement limits the co-registration knowledge between the short- and long-wavelength bands in case two separate detectors are used (for MWIR and LWIR).

Note 2: PLACEHOLDER: Potential note about on-orbit characterisation using atmospheric features (cloud top edges and water vapour gradients, ...) TBC.

Parent: MR-O-010 (uncertainties)

This requirement was examined via LPE calculations in [16] and [this document chapter 3]. The inter-band relative geolocation knowledge is an additional uncertainty only applicable to the MWIR channel, because absolute geolocation knowledge is obtained from spectral information in the LWIR channel (via LOS retrieval). Again, a linear error model is applied (in terms of spatial correlations), however, in this case no constraint is applied at the lower edge. Therefore, two independent random vectors (one applied at the lower edge, the other at the upper edge) are used for constructing the MC ensemble with 100 members. As can be seen in Figure 16 the inter-band geolocation knowledge uncertainty affects retrieval targets with spectral signatures in the short-wavelength band, i.e. CO, NO, NO₂ and H₂O at higher altitudes. Induces uncertainties are 5-10% of the total uncertainty budget reaching about 20% in case of CO in the troposphere.

These uncertainties could further be reduced by in-flight calibration. This has been examined for PREMIER in [50] by exploiting cloud-affected scenes via spectral channel-dependent cloud height determination. For PREMIER, it has been shown that the inter-band relative geolocation knowledge could be further reduced to ~ 20 m. A similar method could be applied also to CAIRT.

1.22 Pointing performance – across-track (ACT)

MR-M-370

Pointing stability (performance) – across-track (ACT)

The horizontal across-track stability of a geometric tangent point over the acquisition time of any single interferogram shall be ≤ 2 km (when calculated as the Root Mean Square Error); this condition shall apply for a confidence level of 99% when evaluated over any orbit.

Note 1: This value corresponds to roughly 10% of a spatial sub-sample.

An across-track stability requirement of about a 10th of the across-track sub-sample size is judged to be sufficient regarding the much smaller horizontal gradients compared to vertical one (e.g. of pressure, temperature and concentrations shown to vary by at least 50-100 times less than in vertical direction [27]).

1.23 Signal dynamic range

MR-M-380

Signal dynamic range

The iFTS shall measure input spectral radiance from sources with zero input spectral radiance to sources with an equivalent black body brightness temperature of 240 K.

Parent: MR-O-010 (regions)

The diverse thermal and density conditions encountered throughout the middle atmosphere result in a wide dynamic range of radiances in the limb view against a cold deep space background. At high altitudes, the atmosphere has very low density, and emits in few spectral lines. In contrast, in the lowermost troposphere, emission approaches that of a blackbody at the prevailing atmospheric temperature, mainly due to emission by water vapour (see Figure 1). At any altitude, the spectral radiance associated with individual spectral lines can be integrated and represented as an equivalent blackbody temperature within a specific spectral band. For the CAIRT instrument, the dynamic range of input radiances to be measured across the vertical swath spans from 240 K at the lower altitudes to just several tens of Kelvins at the higher altitudes (Figure 9).

An equatorial atmosphere may exceed a value of 240 K equivalent blackbody temperature in the LWIR channel in the free troposphere (above the 4-km lower boundary of the FoV targeted by CAIRT, red line in Figure 9). However, the water vapour optical depth is expected to be so large that limb sounding retrievals are challenging or impossible here, so that 240 K remains justified as an upper limit.

Figure 9 Scene equivalent blackbody brightness temperatures as a function of altitude, for polar night (blue), mid-latitude day (green), and equatorial day (red) atmospheres, plotted separately for the LWIR (solid) and MWIR (dashed) spectral bands.

1.24 Radiometric sensitivity (NESR)

MR-M-390

Radiometric sensitivity (NESR)

The radiometric sensitivity (or Noise-Equivalent Spectral Radiance NESR) of the L1b data spectral samples shall be less than the values provided in Table 1 (1 σ specification), when observing a scene with zero input spectral radiance. The required NESR values are applicable for a spatial sample of 50 km x 1 km (ACT x VER).

Note 1: The shot noise associated with the instrument background radiance must be included in the NESR budget.

Note 2: The performance budget for the NESR should also be provided, for reference, including the shot noise associated with the atmospheric scene at the higher limit of the dynamic range.

Note 3: The NESR values between the tabulated ones are constructed by linear interpolation.

Note 4: The NESR values applicable at smaller spectral sampling are constructed by scaling with the inverse square root of the ratio of the two spectral sampling values:

$$NESR_{x \text{ cm}^{-1}} = NESR_{0.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}} \cdot \sqrt{0.2 \text{ cm}^{-1} / x \text{ cm}^{-1}}$$

Note 5: The NESR values applicable for spatial (sub-)samples of different size are constructed by scaling with the inverse square root of the ratio of the samples' project areas (ACT x VER) or solid angles:

$$NESR_{spt} = NESR_{nom} \cdot \sqrt{(ACT_{nom} \cdot VER_{nom}) / (ACT_{spt} \cdot VER_{spt})}$$

Note 6: This requirement is applicable after scaling to the virtual spatial sample grid. Values are also to be provided and reported on the physical spatial sample or sub-sample grid for ingestion into the L2 product retrievals.

Note 7: NESR measurements are expected to be provided alongside measured radiance spectra, but on a coarser spectral sampling grid.

Note 8: NESR is assumed to follow a Gaussian distribution.

Parent: MR-O-010 (uncertainties)

Table 1 Noise-Equivalent Spectral Radiance (NESR) specification for CAIRT. Breakthrough specification is an intermediate level between "threshold" and "goal" which, if achieved, would result in significant improvement for the targeted application. Where specified, the breakthrough NESR is an important benchmark for achieving upper atmosphere mission objectives in full; values around the breakthrough (or better) should therefore be targeted for CAIRT. Nominal scientific performance simulations supporting the MRD are based on the breakthrough values where they exist (and on threshold elsewhere).

Wavenumber [cm ⁻¹]	NESR [nW/(cm ² sr cm ⁻¹) @ 0.2 cm ⁻¹ spectral sampling		
	Goal	Breakthrough	Threshold
718	28.0	#N/A	42.0
750	17.0	#N/A	25.5
800	9.0	#N/A	13.5
1500	17.0	#N/A	25.5
1550	34.0	#N/A	51.0
1590	4.0	6.0	18.0

1650	2.1	3.2	9.5
2150	2.8	4.2	12.6
2200	5.5	8.3	24.8

NESR is the main quantity determining the quality of retrievals in terms of uncertainty as well as spatial (vertical and horizontal) resolution. This connection between spatial resolution and uncertainty is the consequence of the applied constrained (regularized) tomographic retrieval approach and the applied metrics for L2 requirements based on the concept to view the retrieved state as an estimate of the smoothed truth [28], [29], [30].

The NESR has initially been evaluated by 1d linear retrievals [31]. Using the LPE, linear 2d retrievals have been performed as reported in [16] and [this document chapter 3]. As can be seen in Figure 16, radiometric sensitivity is by far the determining factor compared to other tested terms of the uncertainty budget. Only for tropospheric temperature and water vapour, SF6, CFC-11, upper stratospheric N2O5 and PAN, radiometric calibration and ISRF knowledge uncertainties are slightly higher.

Values have been derived iteratively to meet the L2a geophysical uncertainty and spatial resolution requirements for all primary targets. The iteration starts with a generic instrument NESR performance baseline based on literature and the experience gained with the GLORIA airborne demonstrator. This allows to define the “shape” of the requirement to account for physical properties and engineering constraints. The NESR specification is defined over the waveband:

- The longwave NESR specification is driven by the need to retrieve temperature accurately at higher altitudes using a CO2 Q-branch at the lowest wavenumber;
- In the upper layers, the only remaining spectral emission of note emanates from NO and CO in the mid-wave and CO2 in the longwave. The signal from these lines is weak, imposing additional averaging of spatial samples and the use of multiple micro-windows to reduce the noise. The NESR must therefore be low enough to detect the faint signal and satisfy the retrieval uncertainty and spatial resolution requirements.

The NESR requirement is challenging to meet and drives the design of the detection chain. Therefore, detailed parametric assessments of this requirement have been conducted. Several levels are depicted in Figure 10. For the longwave infrared (LWIR), goal (G) and threshold (T_{LWIR}) NESR, and for the mid-wave infrared (MWIR), goal (G), breakthrough (B_{MWIR}) and threshold ($T_{MWIR} = 3 \times B_{MWIR}$) NESR. This choice for TMWIR affects the capability for spatially resolving upper atmospheric features and Science Objective 3 primarily: values around the breakthrough (B_{MWIR}) or better should be targeted.

Figure 10 Radiative Transfer Model calculations of total limb spectral radiances at 100, 50, and 10 km tangent point altitudes, at 0.2 cm⁻¹ spectral sampling. Also shown are the (G) goal, (B) breakthrough, and (T) threshold NESR requirements for a scene with zero input radiance; the additive error (radiometric offset) requirement, and the spectral radiance of a 240 K blackbody. NESR values specified are for 0.2 cm⁻¹ spectral sampling and 50×1 km² (ACTxVER) spatial sampling and need scaling for different sampling.

1.25 A/D conversion - discretization

MR-M-400

Noise discretisation/radiometric resolution (placeholder)

Especially in the upper atmosphere, limb radiance signals are very small, and significant averaging of measurements, in across-track and along-track directions and at times over multiple orbits (zonal averaging) is required to extract information during the retrieval process. Small signals below the NESR floor may need to be averaged, and it is thus important that spectral radiance below the NESR is appropriately discretised. This implies that the noise statistics must not be artificially skewed, for instance during analogue-to-digital conversion with unsuitable bit-depth during the discretisation of read-out interferograms (TBC).

The impact of discretisation error has been assessed for different assumptions of on-board detector read-out pixel discretisation and co-addition schemes, by calculating error spectra and impacts on L2a products. For each L2a product, altitude profiles of the ratio between discretisation error and spectral noise error have been computed under the assumption of threshold L2a vertical resolution [32].

Discretisation noise was found to depend strongly on the number of read-out pixels, because spectral noise and subsequent averaging help to mediate bit-discretisation effects. Preliminary tests and assumptions suggest a 14-bit conversion of the measured interferograms on multiple read-out pixels per spatial sample to lead to sufficiently small discretisation compared to spectral noise [32].

1.26 Bad and dead sub-samples

MR-M-410

Bad and dead sub-samples

The sensitivity values specified in MR-M-390 (goal or threshold) may be exceeded by a factor of two for $\leq 10\%$ of the L1b spatial sub-samples (bad sub-samples), and by an indefinite factor for $\leq 2\%$ of the L1b spatial sub-samples (dead sub-samples), avoiding adjacent dead sub-samples.

Note 1: This requirement is applicable on the physical spatial sub-sample grid.

The impact of defective sub-samples on tomographic retrievals is similar to that of gaps tolerated within the context of the requirement for contiguous measurements (MR-M-050). The main difference is that sampling gaps are likely evenly distributed, whilst the distribution of dead sub-samples is unpredictable.

A similar sensitivity analysis to assess the impact of dead sub-samples on the retrieval of GW parameters was carried out as for requirement MR-M-050 [33]. This analysis suggests that for up to 10% defective sub-samples, there is little degradation of the retrieved GW parameters, wavelength spectra and zonal mean GWMF, and minor impact on phase speed-direction spectra. Up to 10% defective pixels are thus deemed unlikely to affect the GW analyses strongly, and are likely to have a lesser impact compared to the tolerated systematic sampling gaps.

1.27 Radiometric scaling uncertainty

MR-M-420

Radiometric scaling uncertainty

The radiometric scaling uncertainty that is spectrally and temporally and spatially correlated (full correlation) shall be < 1%.

The radiometric scaling uncertainty that is either spectrally, and/or temporally, and/or spatially correlated, but not all at once (partial correlation), shall be:

< 0.25% for wavenumbers $\leq 1500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$;

< 1% for wavenumbers $> 1590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The preceding values are specified for a confidence level of 68%.

Note 1: Fully uncorrelated uncertainties are controlled by the sensitivity requirement.

Note 2: It is not required to prove compliance to MR-M-420 at radiation levels below the values indicated by MR-M-430.

Note 3: This requirement is applicable on the physical spatial sample grid.

Note 4: The scaling uncertainty applies to values after non-linearity corrections and after including any non-linearity term(s) in the uncertainty budget.

Note 5: For the scientific assessment and justification of this requirement, partial correlation is assumed for: a reduced MOPD inducing local spectral correlation, subsequent calibration cycles inducing temporal correlation over the duration of the calibration period, and spatially uncorrelated calibration noise.

Parent: MR-O-010 (uncertainties)

Radiometric scaling uncertainties have been tested in case of 2d linear tomographic retrievals by use of the LPE [16] and [this document chapter 3]. These terms are one of the major sources of uncertainty (after NESR), mainly affecting temperatures below 70 km, upper stratospheric ozone and NO₂, stratospheric HCFC-22, tropospheric water vapour, and tropospheric PAN (see Figure 16). Therefore, there are not many opportunities for relaxation of this requirement.

1.28 Radiometric additive uncertainty

MR-M-430

Radiometric additive uncertainty

The radiometric additive uncertainty shall be $< 3 \text{ nW}/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ sr cm}^{-1})$ in the spectral region $718\text{-}1500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $< 0.3 \text{ nW}/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ sr cm}^{-1})$ in the spectral region $1590\text{-}2200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The preceding values are specified for a confidence level of 68%.

Note 1: This requirement is applicable on the physical spatial sample grid.

Parent: MR-O-010 (uncertainties)

Radiometric additive error has been tested in case of 2d linear tomographic retrievals by use of the LPE [16] and [this document chapter 3]. Additive errors are assumed to be uncorrelated in the spatial domain and have a correlation length of 10 cm^{-1} in the spectral domain. An uncertainty reduction due to ACT binning in the retrieval is considered in the LPE calculations in [this document chapter 3]. As in case of radiometric scaling error, this term is one of the larger sources of uncertainty (after NESR), mainly affecting targets with broader features in the spectrum, i.e. CFC-11, N2O5, and PAN (see Figure 16).

1.29 Deep space calibration altitude

MR-M-440

Deep space calibration altitude

The minimum observation altitude of any spatial sample during an in-orbit deep space offset characterisation measurement shall be ≥ 350 km.

A major source of NLTE emission in the thermosphere that could perturb deep space calibration is associated with NO. In the lowermost thermosphere-ionosphere, NO emission is highly dependent on geomagnetic conditions. During a geomagnetic storm, NO emission at 190 km can be on par with the specified NESR in the MWIR band. A systematic radiance error by NO contamination of less than a factor 10 of the specified additive uncertainty (MR-M-430) is sought. Based on NO radiance measurements with TIMED/SABER, various assumptions on the radiometric calibration approach and additional uncertainty margins, a minimum deep space calibration “tangent point” altitude above 350 km is recommended to avoid contamination by NO emission during geomagnetic storms at high latitudes. For any residual lines, shaving off isolated spectral lines could be sufficient. It has been analysed in [34].

1.30 Spectral ghosts

MR-M-450

Spectral ghosts

Spectral ghosts shall be smaller than two times the NESR.

Note 1: This requirement explicitly excludes ghosts caused by amplitude modulation resulting from pointing instabilities. It controls ghosts caused by phase modulation and by internal amplitude modulation (e.g., by vibrations of optical elements).

Note 2: Spectral ghosts are constrained by this requirement, and do not need to be accounted for in the NESR and ISRF budgets.

Spectral phase ghosts can arise due to vibrations of optical elements of the instrument and lead to enhanced noise values at distances from strong spectral lines [35]. The influence of such perturbations on L2 results can only in detail be studied when a realistic instrument model is available. The values given in the requirement is, thus, only a first estimate.

1.31 Co-registration (CAIRT – MetOp-SG)

MR-G-030

Spatial co-registration (CAIRT – MetOp-SG)

The CAIRT lowermost sub-tangent point P_0 shall not deviate from the MetOp-SG-A sub-satellite point by more than +/- 500 km in the across-track direction **TBC**.

The synergistic use of different measurements can be exploited when the instruments observe the same air masses simultaneously. Co-located measurements from limb and nadir sounders offer complementary perspectives. Although the extended horizontal geometry of limb observations complicates the definition of “coincident air masses,” a form of spatial coincidence can still be established. This is possible because the majority of the limb signal originates near the tangent point.

A spatial coincidence between limb and nadir observations is therefore defined when the sub-satellite point of the nadir instrument lies near the tangent region of the limb line of sight. The lowest tangent point is used as the reference for this alignment. To enable such coincidences, the two satellites must follow the same orbit with a phase difference of approximately 27.5° , corresponding to a time lag of about 7 minutes.

However, when considering individual limb and nadir observations, the areas they sample differ significantly. The formation flying capability of the satellites enables the combination of multiple consecutive limb observations with a sequence of nadir measurements taken at regular intervals. This approach effectively expands the spatial coverage of coincident measurements.

Requirement **MR-G-030** has to ensure that all across-track observations by CAIRT fall within the Field of View (FOV) of IASI-NG.

The CAIRT swath is defined as the across-track extent at the lowest tangent altitude (**MR 1080**). Beyond this point, the across-track width increases as a function of altitude along the line of sight due to geometric spreading. To account for the contribution of regions beyond the tangent point, the overlap requirement is extended to include a larger swath encompassing altitudes above the tangent point, up to a defined limit.

Assuming both instruments have their FOVs centered on their respective ground tracks, the spatial co-registration requirement translates into a constraint on the maximum allowable horizontal distance between their ground tracks. Purely geometric calculations (see [8]) provide this threshold distance to ensure complete containment of the CAIRT FOV within that of IASI-NG.

Two scenarios were considered in these calculations:

1. **Full IASI-NG FOV:** All pixels are included.
2. **Restricted IASI-NG FOV:** Excludes the two outermost pixels on either side of the swath, limiting the maximum across-track sampling distance to 60 km. This ensures at least one nadir pixel corresponds to each CAIRT across-track observation within a 60 km tolerance.

Table 2 summarizes the maximum permissible distance between the two satellite ground tracks at various altitudes beyond the lowest tangent point. Distances are reported both on a plane tangent to Earth's surface and projected onto the Earth's surface. The inclusion of line of sight contribution up to altitudes of 20-30 km beyond the tangent point surely represent a conservative criterium. Acceptable separations range from 500–550 km for the restricted IASI-NG FOV scenario, and up to 600–650 km for the full IASI-NG FOV case.

IASI-NG applies a yaw correction to maintain alignment between its FOV and the satellite ground track [see Sect. 5.1.5 of [51]. In contrast, CAIRT's yaw correction strategy, detailed in Section 6 of [52], is designed to align the lines of sight of consecutive acquisitions for tomographic retrievals. As a result, the lowermost sub-tangent point (P0) is not necessarily aligned with the CAIRT ground track.

The third column of Table 3 shows how the distance between P0 and the CAIRT ground track varies with latitude. When combined with the inter-satellite ground track separation (second column), due to the time delay between the two satellites and the Earth's rotation (this separation is approximately 194 km at the equator and decreases following the cosine of the latitude), we have an estimate of the maximum horizontal distance between P0 and the IASI-NG ground track under ideal alignment conditions, and supposing, in a conservative approach, that both the movements occur on the same side.

Importantly, the largest P0 offsets (column 3) occur when the separation between the satellite ground tracks (column 2) is minimal. Therefore, the effective across-track distance between P0 and the IASI-NG trace is typically less than 200–250 km. This is well within the 500–550 km co-registration requirement, which ensures that the entire CAIRT FOV remains well within the IASI-NG swath.

Table 2 Maximum allowed distance between IASI-NG and CAIRT ground tracks ensuring that the entire CAIRT FOV remains within the IASI-NG swath. Different assumptions of altitude relevant for lowest tangent altitude and different IASI-NG useful range are done. The maximum allowed distance is provided on a plane tangent to the earth surface and on ground.

Selected altitude [km]	IASI-NG Angle for the useful range [degree]	Allowed distance between the two ground tracks for CAIRT swath = 400 km and IASI-NG angle of col 2 on a plane tangent to the surface [km]	Same as Column 3 but projected on ground [km]	Total IASI-NG Angle [degree]	Same as col 3 but for IASI-NG of col 5 [km]	Same as Column 6 but projected on ground [km]
10	42.92	533	549	46.5	633	660
20	42.92	513	527	46.5	612	636
30	42.92	497	509	46.5	594	616
40	42.92	482	493	46.5	577	597
50	42.92	467	477	46.5	562	581

Table 3 Distance between the traces of CAIRT and IASI-NG and between the CAIRT lowermost sub-tangent point P₀ and the CAIRT trace for different latitudes in the ideal conditions of satellite perfectly aligned on the same orbit.

Latitude [°]	Distance between the two ground tracks of CAIRT and IASI-NG due to earth rotation and satellite time lag of 7 minutes [km]	Distance between the CAIRT lowermost sub-tangent point P ₀ and CAIRT trace due to yaw correction [km]
-80	33	200
-65	82	100
-55	111	50
-20	182	0
0	194	50-
20	182	50+
55	111	100
65	82	100+
80	33	100+

MR-G-040

Temporal co-registration (CAIRT – MetOp-SG)

The CAIRT lowermost sub-tangent point P₀ shall be temporally co-registered with the MetOp-SG-A sub-satellite point within +/- 1 minute.

Note 1: This corresponds to a time gap between observations of the same air volume by IASI-NG on-board MetOp-SG-A and CAIRT of less than 1 minute.

Note 2: In first approximation, an ideal temporal co-registration corresponds to a phasing of 27.5° and a temporal distance of about 7.7 minutes between the two satellites.

This requirement sets a limit on the maximum absolute time difference (in UTC) between the CAIRT having the lowermost sub-tangent point P₀ located in correspondence of the MetOp-SG-A sub-satellite point or of any pixel of the same IASI-NG acquisition. Equivalently, this temporal offset can be interpreted as a spatial displacement in the along-track (ALT) direction between P₀ and the MetOp-SG sub-satellite point at a given time.

In practice, if a perfect temporal match is not achieved, CAIRT will consistently sample each area either before or after IASI-NG, according to the time mismatch. While atmospheric composition in the upper troposphere and above does not typically exhibit critical variability over a few minutes, cloud dynamics can introduce significant differences in the measured radiances over short timescales. Therefore, the temporal co-registration requirement is primarily driven by cloud variability, rather than gaseous composition. This is discussed in detail in [8], Section 3.2.5.

Figure 9 illustrates the combined spatial and temporal co-registration requirements. It shows the ground projection of CAIRT tangent points (with P0 marked with a black star), the IASI-NG footprints from consecutive acquisitions overlapping a single CAIRT acquisition (with MetOp-SG sub-satellite point marked with a red star), the satellite ground tracks (with CAIRT in black and IASI-NG in red).

The spatial offset between the tracks reflects the approximate 7-minute delay between the two satellites. A yellow box indicates the permissible region where CAIRT P0 may fall while still satisfying the co-registration requirements [note that this box should ideally be centered on the IASI-NG track, and the proper CAIRT yaw correction [53, Sect.6] should be applied].

The temporal co-registration requirement may impact the separation between the ground tracks of CAIRT and IASI-NG. For example, an increase in time lag from 7 to 8 minutes increases the equatorial ground-track separation between the ground tracks of the two satellites from 194 km to 222 km, thereby slightly reducing the tolerance of CAIRT of moving away from IASI-NG in the across-track direction.

Figure 11 Ground-projection of single-acquisition CAIRT tangent point grid (green dots) and of IASI-NG measurement footprints (blue circles, single sweep in dark blue) for descending orbit. CAIRT s/c located South (out of frame, looking back), black star is the ground projection of the lowermost centre tangent point, red star is the ground projection of MetOp location. The yellow box depicts the CAIRT – MetOp/IASI co-registration requirement

2 Requirement evaluation with the linear SWB

2.1 Overview

The linear SWB has been used here for evaluation of the CAIRT measurement requirements. It consists of the sequence as defined in the MPEP [36] with the single modules described in the ATBD [37]. This sequence is the same as applied in the Phase 0 SciRec study [16]. The detailed setup for the present study including the differences with respect to [16] are described in the following.

2.2 Validation of the linear SWB chain

The parts of the linear SWB used in this report has been already applied for performance estimation during Phase 0. **Table 4** provides the respective references where validation/verification is described.

Table 4 Summary and references of the linear SWB validation/verification.

Part of linear SWB	Validation/Verification scheme	Reference
Spectra and Jacobian database	Has been produced by comprehensively validated radiative transfer models (KOPRA, GRANADA).	[38]
Instrument simulator	Comparison of radiance results for vertical SEDF and spectral ISRF convolution with KOPRA calculations.	[39]
LPE	1) Comparison of central retrieval diagnostics (averaging kernels, error estimation) with JURASSIC2. 2) Comparison of linear performance evaluation with CEEPS.	[39] [36]
FIS	Planned: comparison of linear performance evaluation with CEEPS.	[36]

2.3 Detailed set-up of the linear SWB chain

2.3.1 Spectra and Jacobians database

For the general calculations, the same pencil-beam spectrally sinc-convolved limb radiances/Jacobians database as during SciRec and described in [14], [16] has been applied.

In addition, perturbation spectra for spectroscopic uncertainties have been calculated. For that, special KOPRA-versions were compiled which perturb (a) the spectral line-intensity and (b) the Lorentzian

(pressure-broadened) half-width for molecules calculated using the HITRAN line-parameters (e.g. H₂O, CO₂, O₃, CO, NO, NO₂, CH₄, N₂O, HNO₃, OCS, SO₂, HCN, NH₃, PAN, C₂H₂, C₂H₆, HCOOH). For molecules for which the spectral features are calculated by use of tabulated cross-sections, as well as aerosols, these are also perturbed within a special version of the forward model (c) (e.g. SF₆, N₂O₅, ClONO₂, CFC-11, CFC-12, CFC-22, PAN, H₂SO₄-liq, NH₄NO₃-sld). (See also section 2.3.3 for more details).

2.3.2 Instrument simulation

Basic parameters for simulation of CAIRT observed spectra/perturbation spectra and Jacobians from the spectra database by the instrument simulator are summarized in **Table 5**.

Additionally, perturbation spectra due to elevation jitter are calculated by a dedicated simulation routine as described in [24].

Table 5 Baseline instrument simulation parameters

Parameter	Setup	Reference
Observing elevation angles	Constant elevation angle difference as calculated for a 5 km tangent point (unrefracted) with 1 km width ($R_e = 6367.4445$ km, $h_{sat} = 800$ km) This results in 115 limb-views from 5 km to 115.13 km unrefracted tangent altitudes (3.77 km to 115.13 km refracted).	[37] [[1] MR-M-140, MR-M-170]
SEDF (inner part)	SEDF inner (Gaussian) part FWHM 1.5 km, total extension: ± 1.5 km (all unrefracted at 5 km tangent altitude)	[37] [[1] MR-M-220]
SEDF (far-field part)	SEDF outer part (diffraction convolved with pixel-width + straylight). Not considered for Jacobi-spectra but for far-field knowledge errors.	[37] [[1] MR-M-230, MR-M-240]
Spectral sampling	0.2 cm ⁻¹	[[1] MR-M-100]
Maximum interferometric optical path difference	2.5 cm	[[1] MR-M-100]
Apodised ISRF	Norton-Beer-Strong apodised sinc-function.	[37] [[1] MR-M-80]

2.3.3 Linear performance estimation

Here we follow closely the description as provided in [16] with updates and additional material included. The formulation of the applied retrieval in the LPE is detailed in [37].

LPE-simulations for the ERS scenarios have been performed sequentially for spectral shift, temperature and line of sight (T+LOS), O₃, NO, NO₂, CO, H₂O, CH₄, N₂O, HNO₃, N₂O₅, ClONO₂, CFC11, CFC-12, SF₆, HCN, HCOOH, SO₂, H₂SO₄-liquid, C₂H₂, C₂H₆, NH₃, NH₄NO₃-solid, and PAN. All simulations are performed for a spectral sampling of 0.2 cm⁻¹, along-track sampling distance of 50 km [[1] MR-M-100] and variable horizontal across-track binning.

All retrievals (except spectral shift correction) are performed as 2D retrievals of the geophysical target parameters in the vertical and along-track domain. The retrievals include as unknowns, besides the target quantity, an altitude- and microwindow-dependent radiometric offset correction which is assumed to be temporally constant (within a calibration period), and a microwindow-dependent extinction profile (CONTINUUM) up to an altitude of 60 km. The spectral shift is retrieved in a first step, jointly with a microwindow- and tangent height-dependent scale (gain) and offset (both not being used further in the retrieval sequence). A spatially constant but temporally variable line of sight correction is then retrieved jointly with temperature. HNO₃, PAN, and CFC-11 retrievals include in addition a H₂O ln(vmr) profile joint fit as measure for reducing systematic error propagation in the upper troposphere and UTLS region. The horizontal (along-track) retrieval grid has a grid width of $\Delta y = 50$ km. The vertical grid is variable, i.e.:

- 0, 1, 2, ..., 125, 130, 135, ..., 200 km for NO and CO;
- 0, 1, 2, ..., 120 km for T+LOS, O₃, H₂O, CH₄, and N₂O;
- 0, 1, 2, ..., 80, 85, 90, 100, 120 km for HNO₃;
- 0, 1, 2, ..., 70, 75, 80, 90, 100, 120 km for other targets.

Tikhonov first order regularization is applied in both horizontal and vertical dimensions for the target quantities (and for H₂O in the vertical direction if joint-fitted). Regularization strength profiles were adjusted in order to meet L2 requirements. For the radiometric offset, a diagonal (optimal estimation type) constraint was employed. Its strength was adjusted according to the offset uncertainty [[1] MR-M-430] with the exception of CO, HNO₃, and PAN where the strength has been modified to optimize the trade-off between residual radiometric offset errors and the increase of measurement noise errors. IMK-IAA microwindow selections have been used in the retrievals with modifications for T+LOS, O₃, NO₂, CFC11, SF₆, HCN, and PAN.

Error sources, are listed in **Table 7**. Their implementation is based on the following assumptions:

- **Noise, MR-M-390:** Measurement noise has been considered following the threshold NESR requirements [[1] MR-M-390 and table therein] for a spectral sampling of 0.2 cm⁻¹.
- **Calibration, MR-M-420, MR-M-430:** The spectrally and spatially uncorrelated contributions to radiative scaling and additive errors [[1] MR-M-420, MR-M-430] are assumed to have a spectral correlation length of 10 cm⁻¹. This is implemented by Monte Carlo (MC) simulations with random perturbations of the spectra at each tangent height and every 10 wavenumbers (linear interpolation in between). The MC simulation includes 100 members.
- **Pointing absolute, MR-M-320:** Absolute pointing errors [[1] MR-M-320] are not considered since a spatially constant line of sight correction is retrieved together with temperature from the <1550 cm⁻¹ spectral region.

- **Pointing relative, MR-M-330, MR-M-350:** Intra-band relative pointing errors [[1] MR-M-330] are applied to the entire spectral range while inter-band relative pointing errors [[1] MR-M-350] are applied to microwindows at $>1550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, only. A conversion factor between geometric height at tangent point and elevation angle of $3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ rad/km}$ was applied. Following discussions at SciRecPM04, relative pointing errors are assumed to be linearly correlated along the vertical dimension. The inter-band relative pointing error [[1] MR-M-350, applied to $>1550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$] is simulated by applying uncorrelated random elevation angle displacements at the upper and lower edge of the vertical FOV and linear interpolation in between. Regarding the intra-band error [[1] MR-M-330, applied to the entire spectral range], the random displacement is only applied at the upper edge since displacements at the lower edge are entirely captured by the LOS retrieval. The impact of relative pointing errors on L2 retrieval is estimated with MC simulations of 100 members.
- **Pointing relative, MR-M-340:** Relative geolocation knowledge - spectral (intra-band) [[1] MR-M-340] uncertainties are not explicitly considered in the following since, with an uncertainty of 25 m, they constitute only a slight modulation of MR-M-330 spatial relative geolocation knowledge requirement with altitude.
- **ISRF knowledge, MR-M-110:** ISRF knowledge error refers to the maximum of unapodized ISRF. Apodization reduces the error by a factor of 2.
- **Spectral accuracy, MR-M-120, MR-M-130:** In level-2, a spectral calibration retrieval is assumed to precede the temperature/species retrieval chain. Spectral accuracy has been estimated by linear regression of the spectral shift errors from retrievals at 11 dedicated microwindows (extended IMK/IAA selection) covering the $750\text{--}1950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range. The spectral shift retrieval uses spectra from all spatial samples with tangent heights $> 25 \text{ km}$ of one single acquisition. Both systematic and random error components of the spectral shift retrieval have been estimated. In this case, systematic errors include also the absolute pointing accuracy [[1] MR-M-350] since the spectral shift is retrieved before temperature and line of sight. However, for the considered tangent height range ($>25 \text{ km}$), the shift error is dominated by measurement noise (see section 3.27).
- **Error propagation from temperature/line-of-sight:** Error propagation through temperature and line of sight onto trace gas retrievals is considered for all error sources (including measurement noise).
- **CO₂ mixing ratios:** Based on [40] we adopted the following uncertainties for CO₂ volume mixing ratios (vmr_CO2): 0.2% below 30 km, 0.5% at 40 km, 1% within the range of 60 to 80 km, 10% between 90 and 100 km, and 20% at 110 km. For altitudes below 60 km, these values were derived from uncertainties outlined in the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Fifth Assessment Report, accounting for CO₂ seasonal variability uncertainties as well. Above 60 km, the uncertainties are derived from previous comparisons of WACCM CO₂ data with measurements from the Atmospheric Chemistry Experiment - Fourier Transform Spectrometer (ACE-FTS) and SABER, as reported by [41].
- **Non-LTE:** Assumed non-LTE uncertainties are discussed in detail in [14].
- **CO₂-non-LTE:** Note that non-LTE uncertainties linked to CO₂ vibrational states do not only affect the temperature retrieval but also vmr retrievals of other molecules due to error propagation.
- **Elevation jitter:** Elevation jitter has been evaluated as described in [24] for the case of white-noise for a broad frequency band from 0.1-500 Hz. The elevation time series has been calculated assuming a Gaussian standard-deviation of the jitter amplitudes of 25 m [[1] MR-M-360]. The resulting perturbation spectra calculated from all ERS atmospheres have been the basis for the 1d linear error estimation as described in section 7 of [24]. As the pointing-jitter-affected perturbations are not correlated in along-track dimension, it is not possible to apply the 2d LPE uncertainty estimation for this case. Thus, for the performance analysis here, the jitter uncertainty estimations from the 1d analysis are multiplied by the factor $\sqrt{50 \text{ km/hres}}$ where *hres* is the horizontal resolution from the LPE-retrieval diagnostics (see in Figure 12). This effective reduction

of the elevation jitter estimated uncertainty is applied since the 1d analysis refers to one acquisition along-track, while in case of 2d retrieval, several (equivalent to $hres/50$ km), uncorrelated spectra in along-track dimension are used.

- **Spectroscopy:** The way of calculating retrieval uncertainties introduced by errors in the applied spectroscopic databases is not a straightforward task. The used database (HITRAN2020) includes uncertainty codes (see e.g. Table 2 in [42]) for line position, pressure-induced line shift, line intensity and line-shape from which we use the line-intensity and line-shape as the ones introducing the largest uncertainties. For handling the uncertainties, the following decisions were taken:
 - *Line-data uncertainty distribution:* It is not documented, if the HITRAN codes refer to $1-\sigma$ or even $3-\sigma$ uncertainty. Here we interpret them as $1-\sigma$ (as done e.g. for the characterization of MIPAS-Envisat retrievals (P. Raspollini, pers. comm.).
 - *Line-data uncertainty correlation:* The correlation of the errors is also not reported. E.g. each line could be perturbed independently from the other lines (uncorrelated), the uncertainties might be correlated over rotational-vibrational bands (partly correlated), or the errors are fully correlated over the whole CAIRT spectral range. Here we decided to be most conservative and follow the approach which was selected e.g. for MIPAS-Envisat to perturb all lines in the same direction (i.e. fully correlated) (P. Raspollini, pers. comm.).
 - *Cross-sections for heavy molecules and aerosols:* For gases (mainly the heavy molecules) for which no line-data are available, tabulated cross-sections and cross-sections derived from aerosol infrared optical constants are used by the forward model for which the assumed uncertainties are listed in **Table 6**.
 - *Interfering species:* Considering that systematic uncertainties in spectroscopic data can affect the retrieved profiles, leading to bias in the profiles to compensate for these uncertainties, we address this issue in retrieval scenarios where a given species acts as an interfering species. Specifically, for each retrieved species, only the systematic spectroscopic uncertainty components associated with the target species are accounted for, while contributions arising from the interfering species are excluded. This approach is based on the assumption of sequential retrieval of interfering species where the strongest interfering species are retrieved prior to the actual target species. It is also valid if interfering species are retrieved in combination with the target species (P. Raspollini, pers. comm.).
 - *Error propagation from temperature retrieval:* Propagation of uncertainties induced by the spectroscopy of CO₂ on the species retrievals has been included explicitly (see parameters ‘spint-all’ and ‘sphw-all’ in **Table 7** and Figure 12).

Table 6 Assumed uncertainties for tabulated (gas) and derived (aerosol*) infrared absorption cross-sections.

Cross-section species/aerosol	Assumed uncertainty	Reference
CFC-11	3%	[43]
CFC-12	4%	[44, p. 20]
HCFC-22	3%	[45]
SF6	3%	[46]
ClONO2	2.5%	[47]
N2O5	5%	[47], [48]
PAN	3%	[49]
H2SO4-liq*	15%	[50], [51], [52], [53]
NH4NO3-sld*	10%	[54]

Table 7 Contributions to the LPE uncertainty estimation.

Abbrev.	Uncertainty	Reference	Value	Vertical corr.	Spectral corr.	Time corr.
noise	NESR	[1] MR-M-390	Table MR-M-390	uncorr	uncorr	uncorr
gain_s	Radiometric scaling	[1] MR-M-420	1%	full	full	calibration period
gain_r	Radiometric scaling	[1] MR-M-420	0.25%	uncorr	10 cm ⁻¹	calibration period
offset	Radiometric additive	[1] MR-M-430	3 r.u. for <1550 cm ⁻¹ 0.3 r.u. for >1550cm ⁻¹	uncorr	10 cm ⁻¹	calibration period
losa_sft	Rel. pointing (intraband)	[1] MR-M-330	100 m	linear displacement	full	full
losb_sft	Rel. pointing (interband)	[1] MR-M-350	100 m	linear displacement	full	full
shift_ret	spectral accuracy	[1] MR-M-120 [1] MR-M-130	variable (0.1-0.6) ppm, see	full	linear	uncorr
ils	ISRF knowledge	[1] MR-M-110	1% of peak value	full	full	full
fov_con	SEDF center FWHM knowledge	[1] MR-M-250	2%	full	full	full
fov2_con	SEDF near field knowledge	[1] MR-M-260	1%	full	full	full
diffrafov_con	SEDF far field (2.5-20.5 km) knowledge	[1] MR-M-270	5.3e-4 (2.5-5.5 km) 6.1e-5 (5.5-20.5 km)	full	full	full
strayfov_con	SEDF far field (20.5-115 km) knowledge	[1] MR-M-270	1.2e-5 (20.5-60.5 km) 5e-6 (60.5-115 km)	full	full	full
jitter	Pointing stability (performance) -vertical	[1] MR-M-360	25 m	full	full	uncorr
spint-tar	Spectroscopic line intensity target	[42]	HITRAN2020	full	full	full
sphw-tar	Spectroscopic line width target	[42]	HITRAN2020	full	full	full

spxs-tar	Tabulated cross-sections target	Table 6	Table 6	full	full	full
spint-all	Spectroscopic line intensity CO ₂	[42]	HITRAN2020	full	full	full
sphw-all	Spectroscopic line width CO ₂	[42]	HITRAN2020	full	full	full
vmr_CO2	CO ₂ uncertainty	[40]	height-dependent	full	full	full
NLTE	Various non-LTE error sources, (see [14], Table 7 therein)			full	full	full

lpe_v3_O3_mrd_thres_ref_2.nc	lpe_v3_O3_mrd_thres_ref_2.nc	Local File
act	across-track distance	—
act_bin	across-track sample size	ID
ak2d	2d averaging kernel of target	Geo2D
akdiag	vertical averaging kernel diagonal	Geo2D
alt	along-track distance	ID
apriori	target apriori	Geo2D
correlated_noise	target correlated noise	Geo2D
doy	day of year	ID
esd_noise	estimated standard deviation of target noise error	Geo2D
esd_noise_flos	estimated standard deviation of T+LOS propagated noise error	Geo2D
esd_total	estimated standard deviation of total random error	Geo2D
fitpar_dof	degrees of freedom	2D
fitpar_nmww	number of microwindows	ID
fitpar_npy	number of y parameters	ID
fitpar_npz	number of z parameters	ID
hres	horizontal resolution of target	Geo2D
lat	central latitude	ID
lev	altitude over WGS86	ID
n_obs	number of acquisitions	—
sol	solar activity	—
sys_CO2-CO2-v2-vv	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to CO2-CO2-v2-vv uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_CO2-M-v3-vt	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to CO2-M-v3-vt uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_CO2-M-vt	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to CO2-M-vt uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_CO2-N2-v3-vv	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to CO2-N2-v3-vv uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_CO2-O-vt	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to CO2-O-vt uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_diffrafov_con	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to diffrafov con uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_fov2_con	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to fov2 con uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_fov_con	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to fov con uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_gain_r	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to gain r uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_gain_s	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to gain s uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_ils	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to ils uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_losa_sft	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to losa sft uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_losb_sft	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to losb sft uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_O+O2+M	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to O+O2+M uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_O3-M-vt	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to O3-M-vt uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_O3-O-vt	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to O3-O-vt uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_O3-Oeq	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to O3-Oeq uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_offset	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to offset uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_shft_ret	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to shift ret uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_sphw-all	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to sphw-all uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_sphw-tar	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to sphw-tar uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_spint-all	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to spint-all uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_spint-tar	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to spint-tar uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_strayfov_con	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to strayfov con uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_tot_sample	total systematic error sample of target	Geo2D
sys_tot_sample_corr	total spatially correlated systematic error sample of target	Geo2D
sys_tot_sample_uncorr	total spatially uncorrelated systematic error sample of target	Geo2D
sys_total	total systematic error of target	Geo2D
sys_total_spec	total spectroscopic error of target	Geo2D
sys_vmr_CO2	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to vmr CO2 uncertainty	Geo2D
sys_vmr_O	systematic 1-sigma-error of target due to vmr O uncertainty	Geo2D
sza	solar zenith angle	ID
vres	vertical resolution of target	Geo2D

Figure 12 Output file of the LPE for ozone retrieval characteristics.

2.4 Capabilities and limitations

In Chapter 1 and Table 1.1 of [36] the main capabilities and limitations of the SWB compared to complete instrument-simulation, calibration and retrieval chain as developed in CEEPS is described.

The major approximation by the LPE for uncertainty estimation is the assumption of linearity, which is the accepted, standard approach [29], [55].

Application of the instrument characteristics from the LPE on atmospheric parameter fields by the FL2S assumes averaging kernels and error estimation from the ERS climatology to be applicable for realistic scenes.

2.5 Comparison to Quality Assurance Framework for EO (qa4eo.org)

The LPE provides the averaging kernels and enables an uncertainty assessment based either on Gaussian error propagation (or Law of Propagation of Uncertainties), via the error covariance, or based on Monte Carlo Analysis, via an ensemble of perturbation responses. Our approach follows the recommendations on unified error reporting as specified by the Stratosphere-troposphere Processes And their Role in Climate (SPARC) activity Towards Unified Error Reporting (TUNER), as presented in [55], [56]. This work sets the baseline that real CAIRT data will be based on the principles of the QA4EO.

3 CAIRT requirement evaluation results

3.1 Overview

Resolution diagnostics, error budgets, and FL2S applications to WACCM model simulations (if available) are presented. The FL2S applications consider the impact of atmospheric variability on the retrieval responses (as they rely on LPEv2 results for ERS). Relatively short calibration periods (60 acquisitions) have been assumed in the FL2S simulations in order to better highlight the impact of calibration errors. Resolution diagnostics and error budgets are compared to L2 requirements which have been adjusted to six atmospheric vertical regions (see Table 9) and are expressed in absolute units.

Table 10 shows the actual level-2 requirement table which has been used for all plots where the calculated performance of the instrument is compared to the requirements. Mind that the parameters T, H₂O, O₃, CH₄, N₂O, CFC-12, HCFC-22, SF₆, CO, NO, NO₂, HNO₃, N₂O₅, ClONO₂, PAN, OCS, SO₂, H₂SO₄-liq have been identified as the main target species of CAIRT while CFC-11, HCN, C₂H₂, C₂H₆, HCOOH, NH₃, NH₄NO₃-sl are important secondary targets.

Figure 14 and **Figure 15** show overview plots comparing the estimated retrieval characteristics to the requirements in each altitude range. While **Figure 14** does not include spectroscopic uncertainties, **Figure 15** also takes those into account.

For the comparison of uncertainties to requirements in these Figures, the estimated uncertainties have been divided by the requirement values (Table 10 and [1]) at each altitude level of each ERS atmosphere. Then, the mean of all these ratios is calculated over all ERS atmosphere and altitude levels within the altitude regions (from Table 9). These average ratio values are then subdivided into four categories: (1) uncertainty/goal value ≤ 1 , (2) uncertainty/goal value > 1 and uncertainty/threshold value ≤ 0.8 , (3) uncertainty/threshold value > 0.8 and ≤ 1.2 , (4) uncertainty/goal value > 1.2 (see Table 8). These categories are depicted color-coded as in **Figure 14** and **Figure 15**. In the Figures, the top two panels show separately the results for estimated uncertainties due to spectral noise (top) and the rest of uncertainties (second from top). The combined uncertainty (3rd from top) has been derived as Gaussian combination of both error sources.

Table 8 L2a requirement compliance categories applied to L2 performance metrics (G: goal; T: threshold requirement).

Cat.	Performance evaluation	Assessment (example: predicted [p] vs required [G/T] uncertainty u)
1	Exceeds (better than) goal	$u_p/u_G \leq 1$
2	Between goal and threshold	$u_p/u_G > 1$ and $u_p/u_T \leq 0.8$
3	Threshold compliant	$0.8 > u_p/u_T \leq 1.2$
4	Non-compliant	$u_p/u_T > 1.2$

The varying tropopause in the ERS climatology as depicted in **Figure 13** is taken into account when distributing the altitude-dependent uncertainty values into the lowest two layers (the UT and the LS, see Table 9). For plotting a common tropopause, it has been set to 13 km.

For the comparison of vertical and horizontal resolution with the related requirements, the values of the inverse of the estimated resolutions are divided by the inverse resolution requirements. Then the inversed

mean values of all these single ratios over all ERS atmosphere and altitude levels within the altitude regions are categorized for the plots as described above for the estimated uncertainties.

Table 9 Atmospheric vertical regions for L2 requirements

upper troposphere	UT	5 km – tropopause
lower stratosphere	LS	tropopause –30 km
middle and upper stratosphere	MUS	30 – 50 km
lower mesosphere	LM	50 – 75 km
upper mesosphere	UM	75 – 95 km
lower thermosphere	LT	95 –115 km

Figure 13 Lapse-rate tropopause from the ERS climatology.

Table 10 Level-2 requirement table applied for the performance figures. Note that horizontal resolution requirements correspond to an area equivalent to a square of indicated side length.

T	5 - TP	1.0 K / 2.0 K	1.0 / 2.0	50 / 200
	TP - 30	1.0 K / 2.0 K	1.0 / 2.0	50 / 200
	30 - 50	1.0 K / 2.0 K	1.0 / 2.0	50 / 200
	50 - 75	1.0 K / 2.0 K	1.0 / 2.0	50 / 200
	75 - 95	2.0 K / 5.0 K	2.0 / 4.0	200 / 400
	95 - 115	10.0 K / 20.0 K	4.0 / 7.0	200 / 400
H2O	5 - TP	5.00% / 10.00%	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
	TP - 30	5.00% / 10.00%	1.0 / 3.0	100 / 200
	30 - 50	5.00% / 10.00%	2.0 / 3.0	100 / 300
	50 - 75	5.0e+02 / 8.0e+02	2.0 / 4.0	200 / 400
	75 - 95	5.0e+02 / 8.0e+02	3.0 / 5.0	400 / 400
O3	5 - TP	1.5e+01 / 3.0e+01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
	TP - 30	5.0e+01 / 1.5e+02	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
	30 - 50	1.0e+02 / 2.0e+02	2.0 / 3.0	100 / 200
	50 - 75	5.0e+01 / 1.0e+02	2.0 / 4.0	200 / 300
	75 - 95	1.0e+02 / 3.0e+02	2.0 / 5.0	200 / 400
CH4	TP - 30	3.0e+01 / 6.0e+01	1.0 / 3.0	100 / 200
	30 - 50	3.0e+01 / 6.0e+01	2.0 / 3.0	100 / 200
	50 - 75	3.0e+01 / 6.0e+01	2.0 / 4.0	200 / 300
N2O	TP - 30	5.0e+00 / 1.5e+01	1.0 / 3.0	100 / 200
	30 - 50	5.0e+00 / 1.5e+01	2.0 / 3.0	100 / 200
CFC-12	TP - 30	1.0e-02 / 3.0e-02	1.0 / 3.0	100 / 200
HCFC-22	TP - 30	2.0e-03 / 6.0e-03	1.0 / 3.0	100 / 200
SF6	TP - 30	5.0e-05 / 1.5e-04	1.0 / 3.0	100 / 400
CO	5 - TP	1.0e+01 / 3.0e+01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
	TP - 30	1.0e+01 / 3.0e+01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
	30 - 50	4.0e+01 / 7.0e+01	2.0 / 3.0	200 / 300
	50 - 75	1.0e+02 / 5.0e+02	2.0 / 4.0	200 / 300
	75 - 95	7.0e+02 / 2.0e+03	3.0 / 5.0	200 / 400
	95 - 115	2.0e+03 / 5.0e+03	4.0 / 7.0	200 / 400
NO	TP - 30	2.0e-01 / 5.0e-01	1.0 / 4.0	100 / 300
	30 - 50	2.0e-01 / 1.0e+00	2.0 / 4.0	200 / 300
	50 - 75	2.0e+00 / 2.0e+01	2.0 / 4.0	200 / 300
	75 - 95	1.0e+02 / 6.0e+02	3.0 / 5.0	200 / 400
	95 - 115	5.0e+03 / 3.0e+04	3.0 / 5.0	200 / 400
NO2	TP - 30	2.0e-01 / 5.0e-01	1.0 / 3.0	100 / 300
	30 - 50	2.0e-01 / 5.0e-01	2.0 / 3.0	200 / 300
	50 - 75	2.0e+00 / 5.0e+00	2.0 / 4.0	200 / 300
HNO3	TP - 30	2.0e-01 / 5.0e-01	1.0 / 3.0	100 / 300
	30 - 50	2.0e-01 / 5.0e-01	2.0 / 3.0	200 / 300
	50 - 75	5.0e-01 / 2.0e+00	2.0 / 4.0	200 / 400
N2O5	TP - 30	2.0e-01 / 5.0e-01	1.0 / 3.0	100 / 300
	30 - 50	2.0e-01 / 5.0e-01	2.0 / 3.0	200 / 300

C1ONO2	TP - 30	1.0e-01 / 2.5e-01	1.0 / 3.0	100 / 300
	30 - 50	2.0e-01 / 5.0e-01	2.0 / 3.0	200 / 300
PAN	5 - TP	4.0e-02 / 1.0e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
	TP - 30	4.0e-02 / 1.0e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
OCS	TP - 30	5.0e-02 / 1.5e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
SO2	TP - 30	1.0e-01 / 5.0e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
H2SO4-liq	TP - 30	1.0e-01 / 3.0e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
CFC-11	TP - 30	1.0e-02 / 2.5e-02	1.0 / 3.0	100 / 200
HCN	5 - TP	5.0e-02 / 2.0e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
	TP - 30	5.0e-02 / 2.0e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
C2H2	5 - TP	2.0e-02 / 1.0e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
	TP - 30	2.0e-02 / 1.0e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
C2H6	5 - TP	5.0e-02 / 5.0e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
	TP - 30	5.0e-02 / 5.0e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
HCOOH	5 - TP	1.0e-01 / 1.0e+00	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
	TP - 30	1.0e-01 / 1.0e+00	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
NH3	5 - TP	1.0e-01 / 5.0e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
	TP - 30	1.0e-01 / 5.0e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
NH4NO3-sld	5 - TP	2.0e-01 / 6.0e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200
	TP - 30	2.0e-01 / 6.0e-01	1.0 / 2.0	100 / 200

Figure 14 Performance summary over all ERS atmospheres for all products compared to the L2 requirements. From top to bottom: estimated noise (ESD), systematic (sys), total uncertainties (tot) as well as horizontal resolution (hres), vertical resolution (vres) and their product, the spatial resolution (hxvres= hres × vres). Mind that the varying tropopause (as used for calculating the performance separating the lower two layers) has been put to 13 km in these plots. Mind that for simulation of SF₆ zonal means, an average of 28 samples were assumed reducing the instrumental noise as well as calibration uncertainties.

Figure 15 As Figure 14 but including spectroscopic uncertainties.

Figure 16 Contributions (in %) of measurement requirements (all at their threshold values and breakthrough for MWIR-band NESR) to the specified threshold L2a total uncertainty requirements. For each L2a parameter in each vertical/altitude bin (y-axis on the right), the three dominant contributors to uncertainty are in boxes (black/blue/green, in order of their impact). Rightmost columns: total uncertainty (including external sources except spectroscopy) and spatial resolution (hvxres) compared to L2a requirements from Table 4.2, averaged over ERS climatology and vertical bins. Dark green: <G; light green: G-0.8T; yellow: 0.8T-1.2T; red: >1.2T

3.2 Temperature

Figure 17 Diagnostics for T+LOS for the mean over all ERS atmospheres. Left: vertical resolution ($\Delta z_i / (\sum_j A_{ij,ij'})$). Middle: horizontal resolution. Red solid line is along-track resolution $altres = \Delta y (\sum_j A_{ij,ij'}) / A_{ij,ij}$, dashed red line across-track binning (act). The black line corresponds to the area-related horizontal resolution $hres = \sqrt{altres \times act}$ for which the requirements are defined. Right: uncertainty budget. Colour-shaded areas indicate requirements: <goal (green), [goal-0.8x threshold] (light green), [0.8-1.2]x threshold (yellow) and >1.2x threshold (orange).

3.3 O₃

Figure 18 As Figure 17 but for O₃.

3.4 NO

Figure 19 As Figure 17 but for NO.

3.5 NO₂

Figure 20 As Figure 17 but for NO₂.

3.6 CO

Figure 21 As Figure 17 but for CO.

3.7 H₂O

Figure 22 As Figure 17 but for H₂O.

3.8 CH₄

Figure 23 As Figure 17 but for CH₄.

3.9 N₂O

Figure 24 As Figure 17 but for N₂O.

3.10 HNO₃

Figure 25 As Figure 17 but for HNO₃.

3.11 N₂O₅

Figure 26 As Figure 17 but for N₂O₅.

3.12 CIONO2

Figure 27 As Figure 17 but for CIONO₂.

3.13 CFC-11

Figure 28 As Figure 17 but for CFC-11.

3.14 CFC-12

Figure 29 As Figure 17 but for CFC-12.

3.15 HCFC-22

Figure 30 As Figure 17 but for HCFC-22.

3.16 SF6

Figure 31 As Figure 17 but for SF₆.

3.17 HCN

Figure 32 As Figure 17 but for HCN.

3.18 SO₂

Figure 33 As Figure 17 but for SO₂.

3.19 OCS

Figure 34 As Figure 17 but for OCS.

3.20 H₂SO₄-liqFigure 35 As Figure 17 but for H₂SO₄-liq aerosol volume density.

3.21C2H2

Figure 36 As Figure 17 but for C₂H₂.

3.22 C₂H₆

Figure 37 As Figure 17 but for C₂H₆.

3.23 PAN

Figure 38 As Figure 17 but for PAN.

3.24 NH₃

Figure 39 As Figure 17 but for NH₃.

3.25 NH_4NO_3 -sld

Figure 40 As Figure 17 but for NH_4NO_3 -sld aerosol volume density.

3.26 HCOOH

Figure 41 As Figure 17 but for HCOOH.

3.27 Spectral shift

Retrieval uncertainties of the spectral shift correction are dominated by instrumental noise. They show a considerable variability with atmospheric conditions, which is primarily ruled by stratospheric temperatures driving the signal strength of the spectral lines to be adjusted. Largest noise uncertainties are thus found in polar winter conditions. Due to the regression fit applied to the retrieval results of individual microwindows, the error of the wavenumber-dependent correction function varies with wavenumber, exhibiting a minimum around 1100 cm^{-1} . Systematic uncertainties are often an order of magnitude smaller than the noise uncertainties. They are dominated by the straylight as well as the absolute pointing uncertainty (recall that the retrieval of the shift correction is performed prior to the temperature+LOS retrieval), though contributions by the ILS knowledge uncertainty are not negligible.

Figure 42 Example for the ERS April+45 daytime atmosphere of the uncertainty contributions to spectral shift retrieval.

Figure 43 As Figure 42 but for July -80 nighttime atmospheric conditions.

Figure 44 Estimated spectral shift uncertainties for ERS April +45 daytime atmospheric conditions. Single microwindow shift retrieval uncertainties due to measurement noise are shown as vertical error bars. The grey-shaded area indicates the resulting shift uncertainty after linear regression of the individual shift retrieval results. Red lines show the impact of systematic error propagation on the linear regression.

Figure 45 As Figure 44 but for July -80 nighttime atmospheric conditions.

3.28 Relative contribution of uncertainties

Figure 46 Results from linear 2d tomographic uncertainty estimation (LPE) in relation to the total estimated uncertainty for different atmospheric targets and altitude ranges.

Figure 47

Figure 48

Figure 49

Figure 50

Figure 51

Figure 52

Figure 53

Figure 54

Figure 55

Figure 56

Figure 57

4 Deviations from requirements and mitigation

4.1 Spectroscopic uncertainties

- We use most conservative approach by disturbing all lines in the same direction (e.g. FORUM uncertainty estimation apply entirely random perturbations of line-strengths and half-widths)
- Very uncertain spectroscopic error values in HITRAN – e.g. **Figure 58** shows a retrieved CH₄ profile of a flight with GLORIA-B from Kiruna in August 2021 in comparison with in-situ observations. The difference between GLORIA-B and the in-situ measurements is within 10%. However, the CH₄ error in the GLORIA-B observation is dominated by the large spectroscopic error (mainly line strength and line width) given in the HITRAN database. This is a strong hint that the spectroscopic error is overestimated, since the difference between GLORIA-B and the in-situ instruments is clearly smaller than the combined error itself.
- Need to investigate more closely the spectroscopic error estimates (use e.g. MIPAS/ACE-FTS validation) and improve those where the listed uncertainties are critical.)
- Spectroscopic uncertainties of L2 products are less critical than those connected with the instrument (i.e. L1b and its knowledge). Retrievals can always be improved upon in case an improvement of the spectroscopic database has been performed as long as Level-1 data are available.

Figure 58 Left: All measured GLORIA-B CH₄ data points (orange squares) and mean vertical profile (red solid line) compared to in-situ AirCore (cyan and pink squares) and SPECIES data (green squares) and these data smoothed with the averaging kernel of GLORIA-B (solid blue, violet and dark green line). For comparison, a northern hemispheric lower tropospheric value from the AGAGE network is shown, too (magenta star). **Middle and right:** Absolute and relative differences together with combined error bars and GLORIA-B standard deviation (SD).

5 Literature

- [1] ESA Earth and Mission Science Division, 'CHANGING ATMOSPHERE INFRARED TOMOGRAPHY EXPLORER (CAIRT) MISSION REQUIREMENTS DOCUMENT', ESA-EOPSM-CAIR-MRD-4662, issue 0, revision 4, Feb. 2025.
- [2] M. Höpfner *et al.*, 'Evidence of scattering of tropospheric radiation by PSCs in mid-IR limb emission spectra: MIPAS-B observations and KOPRA simulations: SCATTERING BY PSCS IN MIPAS-B SPECTRA', *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, vol. 29, no. 8, pp. 119-1-119-4, Apr. 2002, doi: 10.1029/2001GL014443.
- [3] M. Höpfner and C. Emde, 'Comparison of single and multiple scattering approaches for the simulation of limb-emission observations in the mid-IR', *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transf.*, vol. 91, no. 3, pp. 275-285, Jan. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.jqsrt.2004.05.066.
- [4] R. H. Norton and R. Beer, 'Errata: New Apodizing Functions For Fourier Spectrometry', *J. Opt. Soc. Am.*, vol. 67, no. 3, p. 419, Jan. 1977, doi: 10.1364/JOSA.67.000419.
- [5] R. H. Norton and R. Beer, 'New apodizing functions for Fourier spectrometry', *J. Opt. Soc. Am.*, vol. 66, no. 3, p. 259, Jan. 1976, doi: 10.1364/JOSA.66.000259.
- [6] P. Raspollini *et al.*, 'MIPAS level 2 operational analysis', *Atmospheric Chem. Phys.*, vol. 6, no. 12, pp. 5605-5630, Dec. 2006, doi: 10.5194/acp-6-5605-2006.
- [7] M. Kiefer *et al.*, 'IMK/IAA MIPAS temperature retrieval version 8: nominal measurements', *Atmospheric Meas. Tech.*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 4111-4138, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.5194/amt-14-4111-2021.
- [8] S. Ceccherini, C. Belotti, B. Carli, and P. Raspollini, 'Use of apodization in quantitative spectroscopy', *Opt. Lett.*, vol. 32, no. 10, p. 1329, May 2007, doi: 10.1364/OL.32.001329.
- [9] B.-M. Sinnhuber, B. Funke, M. Höpfner, P. Preusse, and P. Raspollini, 'Consolidated Inputs to MRD', DEL-11-TN7-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.1, final version, Jan. 2024.
- [10] T. Von Clarmann and G. Echle, 'Selection of optimized microwindows for atmospheric spectroscopy', *Appl. Opt.*, vol. 37, no. 33, p. 7661, Nov. 1998, doi: 10.1364/AO.37.007661.
- [11] G. Echle *et al.*, 'Optimized spectral microwindows for data analysis of the Michelson Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding on the Environmental Satellite', *Appl. Opt.*, vol. 39, no. 30, p. 5531, Oct. 2000, doi: 10.1364/AO.39.005531.
- [12] A. Dudhia, V. L. Jay, and C. D. Rodgers, 'Microwindow selection for high-spectral-resolution sounders', *Appl. Opt.*, vol. 41, no. 18, p. 3665, Jun. 2002, doi: 10.1364/AO.41.003665.
- [13] G. Wetzel, M. Höpfner, and A. Kleinert, 'Quality of the SF6 volume mixing ratio retrieval depending on different spectral resolutions', DEL-12-TN-8.3-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.0, Jan. 2023.
- [14] M. Garcia-Comas, B. Funke, M. Lopez-Puertas, and M. Höpfner, 'Supplement to DEL-08-02-TN4-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC_1.3 - Non-LTE error assessment for CAIRT', Suppl. DEL-08-02-TN4-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC_1.3, Sep. 2023.
- [15] M. Höpfner and B. Funke, 'DEL-09-03-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-3.0 - Technical note on spectral calibration - Version 2', DEL-09-03-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-3.0, Jul. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18496134>
- [16] M. Höpfner *et al.*, 'DEL-08-02-TN4-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC_1.3 - Anticipated Mission performance at Phase-0', DEL-08-02-TN4-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC_1.3, Oct. 2023.

- [17] S. Rhode *et al.*, 'Global-scale gravity wave analysis methodology for the ESA Earth Explorer 11 candidate CAIRT', *Atmospheric Meas. Tech.*, vol. 17, no. 19, pp. 5785–5819, Oct. 2024, doi: 10.5194/amt-17-5785-2024.
- [18] M. Höpfner *et al.*, 'Tracing mission requirements to mission objectives and scientific goals', DEL-10-TN6-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.2, Oct. 2023.
- [19] P. Preusse *et al.*, 'Space-based measurements of stratospheric mountain waves by CRISTA, 1. Sensitivity, analysis method, and a case study', *J Geophys Res*, vol. 107(D23), no. 8178, 2002, doi: 10.1029/2001JD000699.
- [20] M. Höpfner, 'DEL-09-10-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.0 – Technical note on cloud influence', DEL-09-10-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.0, Sep. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18496134>
- [21] J. Ungermann, L. Hoffmann, P. Preusse, M. Kaufmann, and M. Riese, 'Tomographic retrieval approach for mesoscale gravity wave observations by the PREMIER Infrared Limb-Sounder', *Atmospheric Meas. Tech.*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 339–354, Mar. 2010, doi: 10.5194/amt-3-339-2010.
- [22] M. Höpfner, B. Funke, F. Friedl-Vallon, and J. Ungermann, 'DEL-09-04-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-5.0 – Technical note on diffraction/far field SEDF - Version 5', DEL-09-04-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-5.0, Jul. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18496134>
- [23] M. Höpfner, F. Friedl-Vallon, B. Funke, A. Kleinert, P. Preusse, and J. Ungermann, 'DEL-09-06-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-6.0 – Technical note on SEDF requirement - Version 6', DEL-09-06-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-6.0, Nov. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18496134>
- [24] M. Höpfner, 'DEL-09-02-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-5.0 - Technical note on pointing jitter - Version 5', DEL-09-02-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-5.0, Mar. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18496134>
- [25] T. von Clarmann, 'Retrieval of temperature and tangent altitude pointing from limb emission spectra recorded from space by the Michelson Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding (MIPAS)', *J. Geophys. Res.*, vol. 108, no. D23, p. 4736, 2003, doi: 10.1029/2003JD003602.
- [26] T. von Clarmann *et al.*, 'Retrieval of temperature, H₂O, O₃, HNO₃, CH₄, N₂O, ClONO₂ and ClO from MIPAS reduced resolution nominal mode limb emission measurements', *Atmospheric Meas. Tech.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 159–175, May 2009, doi: 10.5194/amt-2-159-2009.
- [27] M. Höpfner, J. Ungermann, and P. Preusse, 'DEL-09-07-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.0 - Technical note on horizontal vs. vertical atmospheric variability - Version 1', DEL-09-07-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.0, Aug. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18496134>
- [28] T. von Clarmann *et al.*, 'Overview: Estimating and reporting uncertainties in remotely sensed atmospheric composition and temperature', *Atmospheric Meas. Tech.*, vol. 13, no. 8, pp. 4393–4436, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.5194/amt-13-4393-2020.
- [29] C. D. Rodgers, *Inverse methods for atmospheric sounding: theory and practice*. in Series on atmospheric, oceanic and planetary physics, no. 2. Singapore: World Scientific, 2000.
- [30] M. Höpfner, B. Funke, and J. Ungermann, 'GMV-CEEPS-TN-04 – Error Propagation Technical Note - Version 5', GMV-CEEPS-TN-04, Jun. 2024.
- [31] M. Höpfner, B. Funke, J. Ungermann, and B.-M. Sinnhuber, 'CAIRT SciRec linear error analysis - Version 3', May 2022.
- [32] M. Höpfner, J. Ungermann, and P. Preusse, 'DEL-09-08-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-2.0 Technical note analog-digital discretization error', DEL-09-08-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-2.0, Oct. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18496134>

- [33] S. Rhode, J. Ungermann, and P. Preusse, 'DEL-09-09-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.1 Technical Note: Influence of calibration gaps and dead sub-samples', DEL-09-09-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.1, Oct. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18496134>
- [34] B. Funke, 'Minimum Altitude of Deep Space Calibration', DEL-12-TN-8.6-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.0, Oct. 2023.
- [35] W. Kimmig, 'Das Abtastverfahren der Interferogramme des flugzeuggetragenen Fourierspektrometers MIPAS-STR', 2001, doi: 10.5445/IR/3012001.
- [36] B. Funke *et al.*, 'DEL-07-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-2.0 - CAIRT Mission Performance Evaluation Plan (MPEP)', DEL-07-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-2.0, Sep. 2025.
- [37] M. Höpfner, B. Funke, Q. Errera, P. Raspollini, B.-M. Sinnhuber, and J. Ungermann, 'DEL-04-01a-ATBD CAIRT-PhAPerReC-2.1 - CAIRT linear SWB ATBD', DEL-04-01a-ATBD CAIRT-PhAPerReC-2.1, Sep. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18496134>
- [38] M. Höpfner and B. Funke, 'DEL-04-01d-ATBD CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.0 - ATBD-KOPRA', DEL-04-01d-ATBD CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.0, Oct. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18496134>
- [39] P. Raspollini *et al.*, 'Verification of mission performance simulation tools', DEL-07-TN3-CAIRT-Ph0SciReC-1.1, Jan. 2023.
- [40] M. García-Comas *et al.*, 'Version 8 IMK-IAA MIPAS temperatures from 12–15 μm spectra: Middle and Upper Atmosphere modes', *Atmospheric Meas. Tech.*, vol. 16, no. 21, pp. 5357–5386, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.5194/amt-16-5357-2023.
- [41] M. López-Puertas *et al.*, 'Validation of the MIPAS CO₂ volume mixing ratio in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere and comparison with WACCM simulations', *J. Geophys. Res. Atmospheres*, vol. 122, no. 15, pp. 8345–8366, 2017, doi: 10.1002/2017JD026805.
- [42] I. E. Gordon *et al.*, 'The HITRAN2020 molecular spectroscopic database', *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transf.*, vol. 277, p. 107949, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jqsrt.2021.107949.
- [43] J. J. Harrison, 'New and improved infrared absorption cross sections for trichlorofluoromethane (CFC-11)', *Atmospheric Meas. Tech.*, vol. 11, no. 10, pp. 5827–5836, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.5194/amt-11-5827-2018.
- [44] J. J. Harrison, 'New and improved infrared absorption cross sections for dichlorodifluoromethane (CFC-12)', *Atmospheric Meas. Tech.*, vol. 8, no. 8, pp. 3197–3207, Aug. 2015, doi: 10.5194/amt-8-3197-2015.
- [45] J. J. Harrison, 'New and improved infrared absorption cross sections for chlorodifluoromethane (HCFC-22)', *Atmospheric Meas. Tech.*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 2593–2601, Jun. 2016, doi: 10.5194/amt-9-2593-2016.
- [46] J. J. Harrison, 'New infrared absorption cross sections for the infrared limb sounding of sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆)', *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transf.*, vol. 254, p. 107202, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jqsrt.2020.107202.
- [47] G. Wagner and M. Birk, 'New infrared spectroscopic database for chlorine nitrate', *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transf.*, vol. 82, no. 1–4, pp. 443–460, Nov. 2003, doi: 10.1016/S0022-4073(03)00169-9.
- [48] L. S. Rothman *et al.*, 'The HITRAN 2004 molecular spectroscopic database', *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transf.*, vol. 96, no. 2, pp. 139–204, Dec. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.jqsrt.2004.10.008.
- [49] G. Allen, J. J. Remedios, and K. M. Smith, 'Low temperature mid-infrared cross-sections for peroxyacetyl nitrate (PAN) vapour', *Atmospheric Chem. Phys.*, vol. 5, no. 11, pp. 3153–3158, Nov. 2005, doi: 10.5194/acp-5-3153-2005.

- [50] A. Günther *et al.*, 'MIPAS observations of volcanic sulfate aerosol and sulfur dioxide in the stratosphere', *Atmospheric Chem. Phys.*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 1217–1239, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.5194/acp-18-1217-2018.
- [51] R. Wagner, A. Mangold, O. Möhler, H. Saathoff, M. Schnaiter, and U. Schurath, 'A quantitative test of infrared optical constants for supercooled sulphuric and nitric acid droplet aerosols', *Atmospheric Chem. Phys.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 1147–1164, Aug. 2003, doi: 10.5194/acp-3-1147-2003.
- [52] R. F. Niedziela, M. L. Norman, C. L. DeForest, R. E. Miller, and D. R. Worsnop, 'A Temperature- and Composition-Dependent Study of H₂SO₄ Aerosol Optical Constants Using Fourier Transform and Tunable Diode Laser Infrared Spectroscopy', *J. Phys. Chem. A*, vol. 103, no. 40, pp. 8030–8040, Jan. 1999, doi: 10.1021/jp991323o.
- [53] C. E. Lund Myhre, D. H. Christensen, F. M. Nicolaisen, and C. J. Nielsen, 'Spectroscopic Study of Aqueous H₂SO₄ at Different Temperatures and Compositions: Variations in Dissociation and Optical Properties', *J. Phys. Chem. A*, vol. 107, no. 12, pp. 1979–1991, Jan. 2003, doi: 10.1021/jp026576n.
- [54] R. Wagner *et al.*, 'High-resolution optical constants of crystalline ammonium nitrate for infrared remote sensing of the Asian Tropopause Aerosol Layer', *Atmospheric Meas. Tech.*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 1977–1991, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.5194/amt-14-1977-2021.
- [55] T. Clarmann *et al.*, 'Overview: Estimating and reporting uncertainties in remotely sensed atmospheric composition and temperature', *Atmospheric Meas. Tech.*, vol. 13, no. 8, pp. 4393–4436, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.5194/amt-13-4393-2020.
- [56] T. von Clarmann *et al.*, 'TUNER-compliant error estimation for MIPAS: methodology', *Atmospheric Meas. Tech.*, vol. 15, no. 23, pp. 6991–7018, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.5194/amt-15-6991-2022.